

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite

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Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGEN STIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Document overview

Project Acronym:	DIAMAS
Project Name:	Developing Institutional open Access publishing Models to Advance Scholarly communication
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Nature: Other	Version: 1.0 Final
Dissemination level	PU

Version history

Version	Created/Modified	Comments
0.0	Authors	First draft (documentation and website)
0.1	Authors	Final draft for review
0.2	Reviewers	Review copy with comments
1.0	Authors	Final draft

Acronyms

CAP	Common Access Point
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution Licence
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access journals
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EDIB	Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging
EQSIP	Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing
ERA	European Research Area
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
OA	Open Access
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association
TSV	Tieteellisten seurain valtuuskunta
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report outlines the development and implementation of the Institutional Publisher Service Providers (IPSP) Toolsuite, a deliverable of DIAMAS Task 4.2. It includes a description of the process that led to the writing of the Toolsuite articles, their review, translation, and online technical development as part of the Common Access Point (CAP). It also refers to partner toolkits as well as the feedback and revisions process, and provides considerations about future sustainability and development.

We define the Toolsuite as a set of tools and resources that support Diamond Open Access (OA) and the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) including a set of high-level articles, in-depth guidelines and links to self-assessment tools, training materials and other resources.

The Toolsuite launched in October 2024 and can be accessed at <https://toolsuite.diamas.org/>. Version 1 of the Toolsuite text is also available as part of this report (see Annex 2) and via <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001342>

The Toolsuite is structured around the seven core components of DOAS. These are: funding; ownership and governance; open science practices; editorial quality, editorial management and research Integrity; technical service efficiency; visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact; and Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB), gender, and multilingualism.

The Toolsuite also includes a glossary of terms, keywords and frequently asked questions (FAQs), background information and two further articles, an introduction to Diamond OA and also an article introducing the concept of DOAS.

All Toolsuite articles have been internally reviewed by project partners before being sent to external review by an independent Editorial Board. In order to maintain consistency with the project's Guidelines deliverable, Toolsuite articles have been translated into Croatian, Portuguese and Spanish. This allows seamless transition across the resources in the Toolsuite.

The design and development of the online Toolsuite were assigned to Pontemedia following the evaluation of their submitted proposal. This includes using Drupal and the establishment of interoperability workflows between the Toolsuite and other components of the DIAMAS Common Access Point.

Regarding the sustainability of the Toolsuite, these fall into two main categories, technical sustainability of the web pages and currency/relevancy of the content.

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Further additions to the Toolsuite are planned during the remaining months of the project. These include, a “toolsuite of IPSP sustainability resources” (D5.3) in month 30 of the project (February 2025) and D4.4 “IPSP training materials” due in month 31 of the project (March 2025). As these deliverables are added the toolsuite glossary, FAQs and keywords will be updated as appropriate.

Ultimately, the Toolsuite will become part of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), which will launch in January 2025. As such, a roadmap for transfer will need to be planned before the end of the DAMAS project.

1.0 Introduction

This report outlines the development of the Institutional Publisher Service Providers (IPSP) Toolsuite, a deliverable of DIAMAS Task 4.2. The task began in month 12 (August 2023) of the DIAMAS project. The project proposal describes the Toolsuite as a “full IPSP toolsuite including the quality and sustainability self-assessment tools built in Work Package (WP) 3&5, an IPSP management toolkit (financial & legal matters, licensing, IT, editorial & production, marketing & comms, funding, and preservation). The toolsuite will also serve as a portal for toolkits elsewhere”.

For the purposes of this deliverable, we define the Toolsuite as a set of tools and resources that support Diamond Open Access and the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS). This includes a set of high-level articles, more in-depth guidelines and links to self-assessment tools, training materials and other relevant resources.

The Toolsuite launched in October 2024 in order to make the IPSP Guidelines available as part of DIAMAS D4.3 (Armengou, et al., 2024) as well as the Toolsuite articles described in this report. Other parts of the complete Toolsuite will be added in the remaining months of the project as they come online. For example, a suite of sustainability resources (DIAMAS D5.3) is due to be added in February 2025 and a suite of training materials (DIAMAS D4.4) will be launched in March 2025. The training materials are based on the structure of the seven core components of the Diamond Open Access Standard (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024a) and draw on the practical recommendations provided in the Toolsuite articles and guidelines.

The Toolsuite can be accessed at <https://toolsuite.diamas.org/>. Version 1 of the Toolsuite text is also available as part of this report (see Annex 2) and via ZENODO at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001342>. Furthermore, in line with the IPSP Guidelines deliverable, the Toolsuite is available in Croatian, Portuguese and Spanish, in addition to English.

This report describes the processes behind the creation of the Toolsuite. It covers the methodology and structure, the writing process and content review. The report concludes with a discussion of lessons learned, how the Toolsuite will be developed during the project and the sustainability of the Toolsuite post project conclusion in August 2025.

2.0 Description of the IPSP Toolsuite

2.1 Methodology and structure

The development of the Toolsuite began in 2023 in parallel to the writing of Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP) version 1.0 (Armengou et al., 2023). At this stage it was decided to use the seven core components of EQSIP to create the skeleton of the Toolsuite. Although EQSIP was due to go out to consultation, and would subsequently develop into EQSIP 2.0 (Rico-Castro et al., 2024), the seven core components were agreed from the outset of the project.

The seven core components are:

1. Funding
2. Ownership and governance
3. Open Science Practices
4. Editorial Quality, Editorial Management and Research Integrity
5. Technical Service Efficiency
6. Visibility, Indexation, Communication, Marketing and Impact
7. Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB), Gender, and Multilingualism

EQSIP was subsequently rebranded as the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS). However, the seven core components remained unaltered. The main sections of the Toolsuite are intended to be high level introductions to DOAS and act as a signpost to DIAMAS resources and further reading.

A number of existing toolkits were consulted in order to inform the structure of the Toolsuite articles. As the IPSP Toolsuite was intended to be a series of high level articles, the format of the OAPEN Open Access (OA) Books Toolkit was seen as a good methodology and structure to follow (OAPEN, 2024).

The OAPEN OA Books Toolkit is a series of short, approximately 500-word articles, which are referenced as appropriate with an additional further reading section that acts as a signpost to other resources. In addition, the OAPEN Toolkit features a glossary of terms, keywords and a list of frequently asked questions. Another resource, the DOAJ/OASPA Open Access Journals Toolkit (2024) was also investigated and found to have a very similar methodology and structure. Permission was sought and subsequently given by OAPEN to adapt the article templates, which were then edited to suite the needs of the IPSP Toolsuite (See Annex 1).

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In addition to articles covering the seven core components, it was decided to create a glossary of terms, keywords and frequently asked questions (FAQs) in order to support the articles. Authors were encouraged to add information where relevant via the template.

There are also a number of shorter articles explaining the purpose of the Toolsuite, how to use it, acknowledgements and how to give feedback and comment. Finally, two additional articles were sought. Firstly, an introduction to Diamond OA and also an article introducing the concept of DOAS.

In addition, the Toolsuite acts as a signpost to other DIAMAS project outputs and external resources. As such, there is a section in each template to note related IPSP Guidelines articles. To integrate this further, both resources were linked to each other during the design and writing process to ensure consistency and avoidance of any overlap (See Table 1). In the further reading section of each Toolsuite article, authors were encouraged to cite other toolkit resources and related literature items, which went into more detail than the Toolsuite or guidelines articles. In addition, the Toolsuite landing page features links to the two published self-assessment tools (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024b). A sustainability and management toolkit and set of training materials will be added upon its publication in 2025.

DOAS	Toolsuite article	Guideline
1. Funding	1.0 Funding	Revenue streams
		Diamond OA policies
2. Ownership and governance	2.0 Ownership and governance	Implementing community-led governance in publishing services
		Copyright, authors' rights policy
3. Open science practices	3.0 Open science practices	Use of open licences in open access publishing
		Research data sharing policy
		Preprints
		Self-archiving policy
		Handling negative research results
		Availability of research protocols, methods and software
4. Editorial quality, editorial management and research integrity	4.1 Editorial Quality	Basic editorial information that should be displayed

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	4.2 Editorial management	GDPR and Personal data
	4.3 Research integrity	
5. Technical service efficiency	5.0 Technical service efficiency	Choosing a platform
	5.1 Software and interoperability	
	5.2 Metadata	Metadata formats and export, identifiers, CRediT tags, bibliographic references, JATS XML or equivalent
	5.3 Preservation and content formats	
6. Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact	6.0 Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact	Marketing, communication and visibility
		Usage and metrics
7. Equity, Diversity and Inclusion	7.0 Equity, Diversity and Inclusion	
	7.1 Gender diversity	Gender diversity
	7.2 Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata	Accessible/ inclusive website, content and metadata
	7.3 Multilingualism	Multilingualism

Table 1. Relationship between DOAS, the Toolsuite articles and the guidelines.

As part of the preparatory tasks for the Toolsuite, DIAMAS partners were asked to identify resources (guidelines, best practices, training materials, toolkits, and other documentation) that would be included in a catalogue of multilingual materials addressing the seven core components of EQSIP/DOAS. These resources could also be cited as references or suggested as “further reading” items in the Toolsuite articles and the guidelines.

In June 2023, DIAMAS launched a community call (June 5 to July 7, 2023) to gather additional resources for the catalogue. The call was advertised on the project’s social media, posted on the website (DIAMAS, 2023), and shared via mailing lists managed by project partners. In response, 50 Open Access resources were suggested through an online form and subsequently assessed for their relevance to the Toolsuite articles.

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Respondents were also invited to express their interest in joining the Toolsuite Editorial Board, as will be further explained in section 2.3 of this report.

At the time of the Toolsuite's launch, the catalogue comprises 200 open access resources in 11 languages (including separate entries for websites and their subsections).

2.2 Writing process

The writing process began with assigning lead authors and co-authors and/or writing teams to each of the seven core components and the two additional articles on DOAS and an introduction to Diamond OA. The lead author was responsible for communication within the teams and as the primary contact for the task leader who acted as editor-in-chief for the deliverable.

Many of the partners in T4.2 were also part of the writing team of WP3, which delivered EQSIP, while others, such as the team at TSV had specific expertise in Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) as task leads of D4.6, the EDIB project deliverable. This also ensured that the EDIB deliverable (Bowker et al., 2024) complemented the Toolsuite article rather than duplicating the work.

Lead authors were each given a template for their section and a set of explanatory guidelines (See Annex 1). The template encouraged a CC BY licence for all project generated content. This was agreed by all authors allowing the whole Toolsuite to be reused, updated and translated as required, either by the project or externally. As noted above, authors were encouraged to add references and further reading as well as keywords, a glossary of terms and suggestions for frequently asked questions (FAQs).

It soon became evident that some of the core components of DOAS would not fit into the desired article length. At this point it was decided to split some of the core components into more than one section in the Toolsuite, as illustrated by Table 1.

At the end of the first round of writing, the articles were circulated between all work packages partners as part of a round of internal review. Partners were encouraged to comment and add any expertise or resources that they had. In addition, this allowed duplication to be identified and for internal links between articles to be highlighted.

Once this round of edits had been completed the articles were combined into one document, which was sent to the Editorial Board for comment (see section 2.3). After this round of external peer review the writing teams made suggested edits and added a number of new references and further reading enabling the Toolsuite to enhance its

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signposting remit. Once the articles were signed off by the writing teams, they underwent an extensive copy edit in order to adopt common terminology, referencing style and overall tone.

Various iterations of the Toolsuite articles were also used to inform the design of the Common Access Point (T4.1) and this will be discussed further in the technical section below (see section 2.5).

The Toolsuite articles were effectively locked for further editing in July 2024 and handed over to both the CAP and the translation teams (see section 2.4). This was done to prevent any changes to the articles while the translation process was ongoing, which could have resulted in discrepancies between language versions.

2.2.1 Glossary

It was decided from the outset that, as a signposting tool, the Toolsuite needed to include a glossary of terms. The first iteration of a DIAMAS glossary was created as part of the preparation for the WP2 Landscape survey (Bargheer et al., 2023). This was used as a draft for the Toolsuite. Article authors suggested glossary terms in each article where appropriate and these were matched with the original glossary. Where there was overlap, the original definitions were revised together with a list of new terms and definitions from the Toolsuite. This was then further revised and edited to form the Toolsuite glossary. Future versions of the glossary will be updated as part of the evaluation and writing process for future versions of the Toolsuite.

2.2.2 Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)

As noted above, FAQs were suggested by the article authors. These were then collated into one document where it became evident that they might overwhelm the Toolsuite. After deduplication and removal of FAQs that overlapped with glossary terms and guidelines articles (which were at the final stage of editing at this time), authors were asked to reduce the number of FAQs per article to no more than four or five. Authors were also asked to provide the answers to their FAQs. This had the effect of further reducing the FAQs to a manageable amount. Although, like the glossary, these need to be kept up to date, with new FAQs added as necessary and redundant ones removed.

2.2.3 Keywords

As part of the article writing process, lead authors were asked to identify terms relevant to the scope of their assigned articles that would be used as keywords to tag the resources available on the Toolsuite. The suggested keywords were compiled into an extensive list, covering the range of topics and concepts presented in the Toolsuite articles and guidelines. The list was then reviewed in order to identify overlapping,

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related, or hierarchical terms. During this process, terms with similar meanings were merged for simplicity and better organisation. Additionally, some terms were grouped under broader concepts or replaced with more accurate or frequently used alternatives, which served as preferred terms.

This review round resulted in a reduced set of keywords, which included commonly used, non-technical, and concise terms. These were subsequently assessed based on the following criteria:

- Frequency of occurrence and relevance to multiple articles/guidelines
- Relevance to other resources and outputs from DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA that will be integrated into or linked from the online toolsuite
- Estimation of subjects/resources users of the Toolsuite might search for, based on the challenges and inconsistencies identified in the DIAMAS landscape report (Armengou et al., 2023)
- Inclusion in the glossary and/or reference in the definitions of glossary entries.

The reduced list contains 25 terms (see Annex 3), which have been mapped to the Toolsuite articles and guidelines, and will be used to tag the CRAFT-OA and DIAMAS outputs that will be integrated into the CAP.

2.3 Editorial Board and review

In addition to the internal review of the Toolsuite articles, it was essential that external reviewers were approached to review the articles. As part of the public call for resources for the Toolsuite, 13 respondents stated that they were willing to participate in further collaboration with the Toolsuite.

These respondents were then contacted to ask them to review Toolsuite components. They were presented with the methodology of the Toolsuite, their expected contribution, and asked whether and how they would like to be involved.

Six of the 13 respondents offered to form part of the Editorial Board. However, due to scheduling and time constraints of the project, only three candidates from Switzerland, Spain and Germany were available to make direct comments as part of the review. The time given by the reviewers has highly appreciated:

- Elio Pellin, Bern Open Publishing, University of Bern
- Laura Rincón, *Geologica Acta*. An International Earth Sciences Journal, Universidad de Barcelona
- Toby Steiner, Metadata & Publisher Outreach Specialist, Thoth.

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The Editorial Board, who were also familiar with EQSIP via the open consultation, were asked to comment on the pitch and relevance of the Toolsuite articles and suggest any amendments, missing information and supporting references. After making extensive comments in the documentation provided, the Editorial Board were invited to an online workshop to expand on any comments and have a general discussion on the Toolsuite. There were no additional comments from the Editorial Board. However, it gave a chance to go into greater depth about the project as a whole and to have the opportunity to thank the reviewers directly.

The Toolsuite authors then reviewed the comments and revised the Toolsuite as necessary. The same process was then adopted for the IPSP Guidelines to ensure consistency.

2.4 Translations

The translation process for the Toolsuite articles followed exactly the same workflow as the translation of the Guidelines. For example, the articles were written in simple common language to facilitate translation (Armengou et al., 2024). Once the Guidelines were translated, the translation teams moved on to the Toolsuite articles using the pilot translation service Mondaecus, an online platform developed by the University of Coimbra that offers a range of features enabling author teams to work (Da Silva Ferreira & Silva, 2023; Silva, 2024; University of Coimbra, n.d.).

The translation of the Guidelines deliverable into more than one European language other than English was a requirement of the project. Although this was not the case for the Toolsuite web pages and accompanying articles, it was agreed that to maintain consistency the Toolsuite should be translated into the same set of languages. Therefore, the Toolsuite and articles are available in English, Croatian, Portuguese and Spanish. This allows seamless transition across the resources in the Toolsuite.

2.5 Technical development

This section outlines the technical structure of the online element of the Toolsuite, addressing key aspects of its development and deployment. While the Toolsuite articles were being written, the Toolsuite website was developed in parallel.

The online toolsuite will be integrated into the EDCH and will serve as an entry point to the tools and resources that DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA are currently developing, as well as other resources relevant to the scope of the Hub.

A public call for proposals for the implementation of some components of the CAP was issued in March 2024, under the coordination of LIBER, the partner responsible for

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overseeing the technical development of the CAP. The call was posted on the DIAMAS website (DIAMAS, 2024) and disseminated via the project partners' networks.

2.5.1 Technical Design and Responsibilities

The technical tasks, including the design and development of the online Toolsuite, were assigned to Pontemedia (2020) following the evaluation of their submitted proposal by an appointed committee of project partners, on the basis of predefined selection criteria.

The proposed technical tasks included the development of the Toolsuite using Drupal and the establishment of interoperability workflows between the Toolsuite and other components of the CAP. The technical implementation began in May 2024 and is monitored by members of the selection committee and the project partner leading the relevant DIAMAS task.

2.5.2 Hosting and Infrastructure

During the development phase, the Toolsuite website was hosted on a Pontemedia staging server for development and testing purposes. Regarding the software stack, the staging server, and the production environment accordingly, utilises the following software components:

- Web Server: Apache or Nginx (latest stable versions) for handling HTTP requests and serving web content
- Database: MariaDB (latest stable version) for storing website content, user data, and configuration settings
- PHP: (latest stable version compatible with Drupal) for server-side scripting and dynamic content generation
- Drupal: Version 10 is employed as the Content Management System (CMS) to manage website content and functionality.

2.5.3 Accessibility

The Toolsuite was developed with accessibility in mind, adhering to the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0 AA standards (W3C, 2008). This ensures that the website is usable and accessible to people with a wide range of disabilities.

2.5.4 Content Structure

The website content is organised into the following main sections:

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- Diamond OA:
 - What is Diamond OA
 - Introduction to DOAS
- Tools and resources
 - Toolsuite Articles
 - Guidelines
 - Self-assessment tools
 - FAQs
 - Glossary
 - Useful links
- About the Tool Suite:
 - How to Browse the Tool Suite
 - Acknowledgements
 - Help and Feedback

Each Toolsuite article includes a "Last Updated" date to inform readers about the recency of the information. This helps ensure users are accessing the most current guidance and resources (For a discussion on versioning, see Section 2.8)

The screenshot shows a navigation bar with the DIAMAS logo and four links: Toolsuite Home, Diamond OA, Tools and Resources, and About the Toolsuite. Below the navigation bar is a blue banner with the European Diamond Capacity Hub logo. The main content area features a large DIAMOND OA Standard logo on the left and a section titled "WHAT IS Diamond Open Access" on the right. The "WHAT IS" section includes a definition of Diamond Open Access (OA) and a paragraph about the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS).

Resources & Guidelines

[Toolsuite Home](#) [Diamond OA](#) [Tools and Resources](#) [About the Toolsuite](#)

EUROPEAN
DIAMOND
Capacity Hub

DIAMOND OA
Standard

— WHAT IS
Diamond Open Access

Diamond Open Access (OA) refers to a scholarly model of publication where publishers, journals, and platforms do not charge fees to either authors or readers.

The Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) is based on essential and testable criteria across seven key components of scholarly publishing to ensure equitable, transparent, and high-quality practices.

[Image 1] - Part of the Toolsuite landing page

2.5.5 Multilingual Support

The website content is currently available in English, Spanish, Portuguese, and Croatian. Drupal 10's core multilingual modules are utilised to facilitate the translation and display of content in these languages.

A language switcher allows users to easily navigate between different language versions of the website and language prefixes or subdomains are used in URLs to differentiate between language versions (e.g., /en/ for English, /fr/ for French). Menu items are then configured to point to the appropriate language versions of pages, ensuring seamless navigation across translated content.

[Image 2] – Caption of the Spanish interface

2.5.6 Visual Style Guide

The website's visual style, including fonts, weights, logo, and colours, is based on the Website, Communication Kit, and Social Media Presence documents provided by DIAMAS (Blake, 2023). This ensures consistency with the overall DIAMAS brand identity.

2.5.7 Security

The website will be served over HTTPS using Let's Encrypt certificates for secure communication in the production environment. Regular security updates will be applied to the server, Drupal core, and contributed modules to mitigate potential vulnerabilities.

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Appropriate user roles and permissions are implemented within Drupal to restrict access to sensitive areas and functionalities.

2.6 Partner toolkits

In addition to the signposting to further reading within the Toolsuite articles themselves, the online Toolsuite also features a section listing a number of other related toolkits in existence. Each toolkit link includes a short explanation to guide readers to this content.

- **New University Press Toolkit:** Supporting and giving guidance to new university presses and library-led publishing ventures (Jisc, 2021)
- **OAPEN OA Books Toolkit:** Promoting and supporting open access to academic books. It consists of short articles covering a wide range of topics relating to OA books, each including a list of sources referenced, further reading and links to definitions of key terms. (OAPEN, 2024)
- **Open Access Journals Toolkit:** Providing guidance for new and established open access journals to navigate the rapidly changing scholarly publishing landscape (DOAJ & OASPA, 2024).

We propose that these toolkits (that share a number of members of the writing team/editorial board) formalise an exchange of information and establish workflows for suggesting updates etc. In addition, we also propose that each toolkit outlines its unique selling point/stakeholder group, which could be used by DIAMAS T7.3 for engagement. It is hoped that a workshop can be organised to initiate the exchange during the remaining months of the DIAMAS project.

Ultimately, the toolkits could become access points to a single shared set of content/resources in the Common Access Point. This is not an aim of the project, but a useful vision to have in mind when writing content and planning for sustainability of the toolkits/suites.

2.7 Feedback and revisions

The planning and writing process was relatively trouble free and deadlines for drafts were purposely set earlier rather than later to enable revisions, copy editing, translations and uploading to the Toolsuite website.

However, this combined with the fact that in any large project, there are multiple tasks and outputs being written at the same time, meant that early versions of the Toolsuite articles had to be extensively revised as other deliverables were written, reviewed and released. One significant change was the rebranding of EQSIP into DOAS. Although the

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seven core components were unlikely to change, the launch of DOAS meant that the introduction to Diamond OA and the article on DOAS itself had to be extensively revised. All other articles also had to be checked for use of EQSIP vs. DOAS. However, the benefits of having text ready early far outweighed the time taken to make these revisions. Most notably, the decision to write the Toolsuite articles ahead of the Guidelines deliverable (D4.3) helped centre the guidelines during that planning and writing process. It also helped to shape the structure of the online element of the Toolsuite.

Another common issue for any project of the nature of DIAMAS is that it cannot happen in isolation. While the pace of change for Diamond OA in the ERA gathered momentum, which necessitated some edits to the Introduction to Diamond OA article, other projects such as CRAFT-OA also needed to be monitored. The DIAMAS project does not primarily address the technical aspects of Diamond OA publishing, while the CRAFT-OA project does not cover the full range of available software platforms and technical issues. As a result, determining the level of detail in the Toolsuite articles on technical service efficiency posed a challenge. However, this content can be revised and updated once the CRAFT-OA resources are released, and user feedback may help enhance the articles.

As part of the DIAMAS EDIB deliverable (D4.6), the authors reflected on their experience of drafting EDIB-related resources for the DIAMAS project, including the Toolsuite articles (Bowker et al., 2024, section 9.0). The main bullet points from that report are worth repeating, as they serve as valuable lessons learned for any project that wants to create a set of resources:

- Make it a collaborative process, but assign a “champion” to prepare drafts
- Remember the scope, but be open to learning from related areas
- Start drafting early
- Use tools to support your process
- Sometimes less is more

2.8 Sustainability and further developments planned

There are a number of considerations that need to be taken into account regarding the sustainability of the Toolsuite. In general, these fall into two main categories, technical sustainability of the web pages and currency/relevancy of the content. It should also be noted that during the preparation of the Toolsuite and Guidelines (D4.3), the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) was soft-launched in September 2024 (see Mounier & Rooryck, 2024). The intention is that the Toolsuite will become part of the EDCH, which will be fiscally hosted by the OPERAS Research Infrastructure. As such, a roadmap for transfer will need to be planned before the end of the DAMAS project.

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In addition, the project is already developing a co-creation and engagement strategy that leverages all CAP components and the IPSP/IPTP network. The strategy will be further described in upcoming project deliverables (i.e., D4.5 IPSP Registry), an initial draft of which has already been shared with the consortium as a project milestone.

The aim is for the CAP and ultimately the EDCH to provide access to guidelines, toolkits, training materials and a dedicated online discussion forum being built as part of the remaining deliverables of WP4. It is perceived that the members of the forum will play a crucial role in sustaining, developing and exploiting the EDCH, including keeping the content up to date.

2.8.1 Technical Sustainability

As an open-source platform, Drupal offers benefits that ensure the technical sustainability of the online toolsuite. It is supported by an active community of developers and allows customisations using built-in modules or plugins, whereas the platform's functionalities are regularly updated and upgraded, ensuring its relevance to current technical, security, and interoperability standards. Moreover, the selection of an open-source platform reduces reliance on third-party solutions or proprietary software that may become obsolete or unsupported as well as the dependency on IT providers who maintain proprietary platforms.

Throughout the project's duration, Pontemedia will undertake the following tasks as part of their assignments:

- Regular security audits of the platform's configurations to identify potential vulnerabilities.
- Regular reviews for compliance with accessibility standards (e.g., WCAG)
- Regular software updates to integrate new features and functionalities.
- Monitoring of the platform's performance and technical support in case of malfunctions.

The long-term sustainability of the online Toolsuite will be ensured through the integration of the platform into the EDCH, which will be developed as a federated infrastructure of interoperable components. Maintenance and upgrades will be coordinated by a dedicated Task Force and supported by structural funds and technical experts.

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2.8.2 Currency/Relevancy

Regarding currency/relevancy, there are a number of issues that need to be taken into account as the content of the Toolsuite (including the Guidelines) are reliant on a number of external factors.

2.8.2.1 Major updates to DOAS

Any changes to the core components of DOAS would clearly have a major effect on the structure of the Toolsuite itself, as well as the content of the high level articles and more granular guidelines. This would also result in a knock on effect for the learning resources and self-assessment tools that are linked to from the Toolsuite pages.

However, in the short term there are no changes planned for DOAS during the life of the DIAMAS project. In the mid to longer term, DOAS will fall under the auspices of the EDCH Quality Management Task Force lead by FECYT and be updated accordingly with feedback provided by the community. At the time of writing, there are plans to review DOAS in the future in the context of a global partnership with Latin American and African partners.

The Toolsuite and associated resources will become part of this network of quality assessment tools and frameworks and be updated accordingly.

2.8.2.2 Direct feedback on the guidelines

While the relevance of the high-level Toolsuite articles is reliant on any changes to DOAS, the guidelines are designed to be expanded as required. The capacity to create new guidelines will rest with the EDCH. However, feedback loops are already being planned as part of other tasks within the project. The guidelines were created after analysis of the EQSIP gap analysis (Brun, Torny, & Pontille, 2023) and there will continue to be a feedback loop via the DOAS self-assessment tool, which will enable users of the tool to highlight further gaps.

Currently, thoughts for the workflow would be to route any feedback given in the self-assessment tool on suggestions for new guidelines to the ECDH for discussion at the Editorial Board. A similar workflow would need to exist for any feedback or discussion in the IPSP forum via the moderator and this is being discussed as part of D4.5 of the project.

The Toolsuite includes a set of keywords, FAQs and a glossary of terms. At the time of writing, these resources refer explicitly to the Toolsuite articles and Guidelines. In the longer term they will be updated as the articles and guidelines are refreshed. However,

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there are also plans within the project's lifetime to add new keywords, FAQ responses and glossary terms as part of the development of the suite of sustainability resources.

2.8.2.3 Translations

The availability of translations creates a potential issue with the currency of the Toolsuite articles and guidelines. At launch, the translated versions are identical to the master English version. However, if the English version is updated in any way, the translated versions will no longer refer to the later version until they are re-translated. This might be compounded if the community translates additional languages. Therefore, each translation needs a version number and also needs to reference the English version it mirrors. As the English version is updated, there will be a clear indication to the reader that the translated version links to an older version. This allows the Editorial Board (see section 2.8.3) to manage the versioning and understand which version each translation refers to.

Furthermore, if translated versions start to become out of date because the translation teams in the community are no longer active or able to provide up to date translations, a workflow needs to be created to retire out of date translations.

2.8.3 Role of the Editorial Board

It is planned to invite the reviewers of the Toolsuite articles and guidelines and the authors of these resources from the DIAMAS project to form an independent Editorial Advisory Board as part of the EDCH.

The role of the Board will be defined by the EDCH. However, it is envisaged that the Board would meet every six months to discuss the currency of the existing toolsuite articles. For example, link rot needs to be monitored as well as the emergence of new resources that could be included in the further reading for each article, and the launch of new toolkits and resources that are of interest. Link rot necessitates the alteration of some of the content and the expertise of the Board would be required to ensure that the articles maintained their original meaning.

Further developments of the Toolsuite	Expected date
Launch of Toolsuite	October 2024
Confirmation of full Editorial Board	November 2024
Launch of European Diamond Capacity Hub	January 2025

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Addition of sustainability resources (D5.3)	February 2025
Addition of training materials (D4.4)	March 2025
First meeting of the Editorial Board	April 2025
Roadmap for the handover of the Toolsuite to the ECDH	June 2025

Table 2. Further developments of the Toolsuite during the project.

2.8.4 Further developments planned

As part of DIAMAS WP5, a “toolsuite of IPSP sustainability resources” (D5.3) will be added to the Toolsuite in month 30 of the project (February 2025). This deliverable will design and develop a collection of resources to support key stakeholder groups in assessing to what extent they are financially sustainable, and providing them with tools and intelligence to help them become more so in the future. Plans are already underway to integrate this within the Toolsuite described in this report.

Another project deliverable, D4.4 IPSP training materials, is due in month 31 of the project (March 2025). As stated above, this deliverable repurposes content from the Toolsuite articles and guidelines into a set of learning resources, and will be linked to from the Toolsuite web pages.

There is also an opportunity to link to a FAIR assessment tool to be produced as part of the CRAFT-OA project and this will be explored by both project partners.

As these deliverables are added during the remaining months of the project, the toolsuite glossary, FAQs and keywords will be updated as appropriate.

3.0 Conclusion

The DIAMAS IPSP Toolsuite brings together IPSP Guidelines that are available as part of DIAMAS D4.3 (Armengou, et al., 2024) as well as the Toolsuite articles detailed in this report.

Additional parts of the complete Toolsuite will be added in the remaining months of the project as they come online. A suite of sustainability resources (DIAMAS D5.3) is due to be published in February 2025, and a suite of training materials (DIAMAS D4.4) is expected to come online in March 2025. The training materials are based on the structure of the seven core components of the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024a). They crucially draw on the practical recommendations provided in the Toolsuite articles and guidelines.

Ultimately, the Toolsuite will become part of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), which will launch in January 2025. As such, a roadmap for transfer will need to be planned before the end of the DAMAS project.

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Annex 1: Toolsuite article template

Adapted from the OA Books Toolkit template with permission from OAPEN. See an example here: [Contracting and copyright | OA Books Toolkit](#)

Title

Main EQSIP headings only

Abstract: up to 50 words

Authors:

Main text: 200-500 words*

This will allow readers to quickly expand their knowledge as appropriate and use the signposted links for more detailed information. The articles should be written in jargon-free language, any necessary terminology should link to the glossary.

* Use the 7 DOAS headings (Funding, Ownership and governance, Open science practices, Editorial quality, editorial management and research integrity, Technical service efficiency, Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact, Equity, Diversity and Inclusion)

Where applicable refer to the major subheading, e.g., metadata (a sub-section in technical service efficiency).

Related Toolsuite Articles

For articles that closely relate to another EQSIP, which you would like to link to.

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

Add links to the guidelines and training materials when they become available

References

For in-text references (or actual source acknowledgement if an article is fully/mainly retrieved from an external resource - please note the copyright holder and terms of reuse

Further reading

Catalogue of Resources

**Funded by
the European Union**

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Search for relevant resources available in English or other if you know the language, tag relevant resources in the catalogue spreadsheet by adding the title of the article in column AD 'Inclusion in the toolsuite' as well as adding them here. Many resources relate to large toolkits and these will be listed in the list of resources in July/August 2023.

Licensing

Ensure that your article can be reused under a CC BY 4.0 licence.

The following sections should be included for use in the CAP

Keywords

Keywords that will show up in the articles and can help users with finding the article based on this keyword. A user will be able to directly go to articles linked to a specific keyword.

Glossary

Any terms (can include, but not limited to, keywords) that may require explanation as the reader may not be familiar with them, that will be part of the glossary list.

Please either check that the terms are in the glossary, making suggested edits if required, or add the terms and an explanation (with reference to an external source, if required) as a suggestion.

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

Please add any FAQs you think users may have and are addressed within this particular article.

Annex 2: Toolsuite components (English, v1.0)

1. Informative texts and menus

1.1 About the Toolsuite

The Tools and Resources pages are a collection of free to access articles, which will assist Diamond open access publishers or those publishers wishing to move towards a Diamond open access model in understanding the basic concepts of the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS).

The pages also include links to two self-assessment tools for publishers wanting to see how they perform against DOAS and also to assess their sustainability.

These pages will also be of use for other stakeholders, including libraries, research performing institutions, learned societies, funders and policy makers.

1.2 How to browse the Toolsuite

The Tools and Resources section is a free to use resource aimed at supporting publishers and other stakeholders learn more about Diamond Open Access (OA) and the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS), which promotes quality in Diamond OA publishing

The Diamond OA section offers articles explaining the concept of Diamond OA and an introduction to DOAS. The toolsuite articles themselves are divided into sections that follow the seven core components of DOAS:

1. Funding
2. Legal Ownership, Mission, and Governance
3. Open Science
4. Editorial Management, Editorial Quality, and Research Integrity
5. Technical Service Efficiency
6. Visibility, Communication, Marketing, and Impact
7. Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB), Multilingualism, and Gender Equity

They can be read as one resource, or standalone articles. Each article provides the reader with a high-level overview of the core component or one particular aspect. They are fully referenced with an additional further reading section. Keywords, frequently asked questions and a glossary of terms are embedded within the articles as well as links to other related articles and guidelines. A set of related toolkits are also provided for further reading.

The guidelines themselves offer a more granular approach to specific parts of DOAS, they can be read as a single set of texts, or referred to from the toolsuite article for more in depth

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discussion. They can also be accessed from the DOAS self-assessment tool, for which they were designed.

There are two self-assessment tools that sit at the heart of DOAS. The links will send you to a separate site which requires registration. They provide an intuitive user experience for publishers to analyse their level of compliance with the DOAS or sustainability parameters. The tool consists of two parallel instances that can be completed sequentially, if desired.

It is advisable to read the toolsuite articles for a general introduction to each component before navigating the self-assessment tool. The guidelines then act as additional support for areas that have been identified as key areas of improvement for many publishers.

These pages and the toolsuite articles and guidelines have been made available in the following languages: Croatian, English, Portuguese, Spanish.

The website content is organised into the following main sections:

- Diamond OA:
 - What is Diamond OA
 - Introduction to DOAS
- Tools and resources
 - Toolsuite Articles
 - Guidelines
 - Self-assessment tools
 - FAQs
 - Glossary
 - Useful links
- About the Diamas Toolsuite:
 - How to Browse the Toolsuite
 - Acknowledgements
 - Help and Feedback

The Toolsuite articles and guidelines are provided as CC BY resources to promote reuse and translation. If you have any further comments on the resources on this page, or wish to suggest a translation team to create an additional translation of the content, please contact the team through the Help and Feedback pages.

Finally, we would like to acknowledge the work of the writing teams, the editorial board, external reviewers and the translation teams that made this resource possible.

1.3 Help and feedback

Please do not hesitate to contact us with any questions or clarifications about this toolsuite and its articles. The Frequently Asked Questions section may also address any queries you have.

To learn more about how to navigate the toolsuite and associated guidelines see How to browse this tool suite.

Feedback

The DIAMAS tool suite will be updated on a regular basis. As Diamond OA publishing develops over time, new terms and articles will be written or expanded, while others may be archived.

Therefore, we are open to comments and suggestions for new and revised content. You contact us via toolsuite@diamas.org at any time. Your suggestions will be then taken into consideration and may be added to future versions of the toolsuite.

1.4 Tools and resources

This section contains a variety of tools and resources to support publishers who are considering moving towards Diamond OA publishing

- **Toolsuite Articles**
A series of high-level articles that explain Diamond OA publishing, the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) and the seven core components of DOAS
- **Guidelines**
A series of more in-depth articles that look at specific areas of DOAS
- **DOAS Self assessment tools**
This self-assessment tool provides an intuitive user experience for publishers to analyse their level of compliance with the DOAS or sustainability parameters. The tool consists of two parallel instances that can be completed sequentially, if desired.
- **Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)**
A series of answers to FAQs selected by the authors of these tools and resources
- **Glossary**
A glossary of terms used in these tools and resources
- **Useful links**
Links to other toolkits and resources of interest to open access publishers and other stakeholders

1.5 Main toolsuite articles menu

These articles are intended to be high level introductions to Diamond open access and the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS). They cover the seven core components of DOAS and also act as a signpost to other resources in this section of the website as well as further reading.

They are also available to download at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001342>

- **Funding**

Publishing services should be able to find a suitable and sustainable mix of funding sources that can be publicly disclosed and do not interfere with editorial decision-making.
- **Ownership and governance**

Diamond OA publishing is driven and owned by scholarly communities. This article outlines how that can be achieved in line with the Diamond OA Standard.
- **Open Science Practices**

Publishers need to be acquainted with Open Science (OS) principles, have them embedded in their policies, and ensure that their workflows are aligned with best practices and standards for facilitating and incentivising OS.
- **Editorial quality, editorial management and research integrity**
 - Editorial Quality
Evaluation procedures used by journals play an essential role in maintaining the quality, reliability, and validity of published contents and must be rigorous, meeting basic standards and generally accepted practices.
 - Editorial Management
Publishers must provide information so that prospective authors and readers can identify relevant journals and easily view their editorial policies and procedures.
 - Research Integrity
Research Integrity (RI) involves conducting ethical research to the highest standards. Core principles include reliability, honesty, care, and transparency.
- **Technical Services Efficiency**
 - Software and Interoperability
In scholarly publishing, an ideal online publishing infrastructure should support workflows from manuscript submission, through peer review, to content display.
 - Metadata
Metadata are crucial for the discoverability and dissemination of published outputs and should follow a set of standards and guidelines determining how metadata should be structured, curated and distributed.
 - Preservation and content formats
Digital preservation enables seamless access to content in case it becomes unavailable on the publisher's platform and should rely on open standards.

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- **Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact**

Deliberate strategies to increase visibility can help published content be disseminated as widely as possible. Traditional marketing activities as well as technical aspects can all contribute to making sure content reaches the intended audience.

- **Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)**

Historical practices have led to discrimination in scholarly publishing, harming individuals as well as research and society more broadly. Actors across the industry can take steps to promote equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB).

- Gender diversity

In scholarly publishing, men are overrepresented as research subjects, authors, reviewers, editors, and executives. Steps to increase gender diversity will help to reduce unconscious bias.

- Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata

Accessibility ensures that people with disabilities can access content, while the use of inclusive language and images helps to ensure that diverse groups feel respected.

- Multilingualism

Multilingualism is the use of more than one language to disseminate research.

1.6 Main guidelines menu

The guidelines offer detailed instructions and practical guidance to assist Diamond OA Publishers in meeting current standards, outlined as the seven core components of the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS).

The guidelines have been translated into Croatian, Spanish and Portuguese, and are also available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13786094>

Revenue Streams

These guidelines provide an overview of the diverse funding mechanisms for Diamond OA, and a framework to ensure transparency.

Diamond OA policies

These guidelines facilitate the implementation of Diamond OA policies in academic publishing, emphasising the importance of accessibility, quality, and transparency.

Implementing community-led governance in publishing services

These guidelines outline how to establish clear processes, policies, and structures to implement community-led governance in publishing services, ensuring regulated operations and decision-making.

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Copyright, authors' rights policy

These guidelines present basic concepts related to copyright as well as best practices in defining and displaying copyright policies for editors and publishers.

Use of open licences in open access publishing

Guidelines for using open licences and distributing scholarly works.

Research data sharing policy

These guidelines help IPSPs implement a research data sharing policy, recognising the essential role of underlying research data in supporting conclusions and reproducibility.

Preprints

These guidelines identify good practices with regard to the publication of preprints that are already available on preprint servers and/or open repositories.

Self-archiving policy

These guidelines describe the essential elements of a self-archiving policy.

Handling negative research results

These guidelines outline a publisher-level policy regarding the publication of negative or unexpected scientific results and data.

Availability of research protocols, methods and software

These guidelines describe measures to ensure that all research protocols, methods, and software are publicly available, accessible, and reproducible.

Basic editorial information that should be displayed

These guidelines outline the details of policies and procedures that should be displayed on a Publisher's website.

GDPR and Personal data

These guidelines explain how IPSPs should handle personal information and comply with relevant regulations.

Choosing a platform

These guidelines help IPSPs understand their technical needs and factors to be considered when choosing an online publication platform.

Metadata formats and export, identifiers, CRediT tags, bibliographic references, JATS XML or equivalent:

These guidelines help IPSPs implement requirements and recommendations regarding metadata and full-text formats.

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Marketing, communication and visibility

These guidelines help IPSPs meet requirements regarding visibility and discoverability, and introduce communication and marketing strategies.

Usage and metrics

These guidelines facilitate the implementation of comprehensive, accurate, and reliable usage and metric indicators.

Gender diversity

These guidelines describe a framework for IPSPs to integrate gender equity into their activities.

Multilingualism

These guidelines provide some practical suggestions to help IPSPs integrate multilingualism into their activities.

1.7 Acknowledgements

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2. Toolsuite articles

2.1 What is Diamond open access?

Abstract:

This article discusses Diamond open access (OA) for journals. In this context, the term 'Diamond OA' refers to a scholarly model of publication where publishers, journals, and platforms do not charge fees to either authors or readers, and where all content-related elements of publishing are directly controlled by the academic community and public institutions.

Main text:

This article discusses Diamond open access (OA) for journals. In this context 'Diamond OA' refers to a scholarly model of publication where publishers, journals, and platforms do not charge fees to either authors or readers. In addition, Diamond OA is community-driven, academic-led and -owned (Ancion et al., 2022; Rooryck, 2023)

But how does this definition translate into practical terms for a publisher or a publishing service provider? The following six operational criteria have to be jointly met for a journal to be recognized as a Diamond OA journal that can be included in the Diamond Discovery Hub currently being set up by the CRAFT-OA (Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access) project, and that will be included in the Diamond Capacity Hub:

1. Persistent identification:

The journal should have a valid and confirmed ISSN (n.d.)

2. Scholarly journal:

The journal should be a scholarly journal that selects papers via an explicitly described evaluation process before and/or after publication, in line with accepted practices in the relevant discipline (Diamas Consortium, 2024)

3. Open Access with open licences:

All outputs of the journal should be Open Access and carry an open licence that is included in the article-level metadata

4. No fees:

Publication in the journal is not contingent on the payment of fees of any kind (e.g. article processing charges or membership dues). The journal should state this as such on its webpage. Voluntary author contributions and donations are allowed, if this is not a condition for publication

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5. Open to all authors:

Authorship in the journal should not be limited to any type of affiliation. Any author can submit an article that is in line with the aims and scope of the journal

6. Community-owned:

The journal title must be owned by public or not-for-profit organisations (or parts thereof) whose mission includes performing or promoting research and scholarship. These include but are not limited to research performing organisations (RPOs), research funding organisations (RFOs), organisations connected to RPOs (university libraries, university presses, faculties, and departments), research institutes, and scholarly societies. The journal should explain its ownership status on its webpage

Important note: These criteria are not meant to theoretically or ideologically define or constrain Diamond OA as a scholarly publishing model. The criteria are merely meant as operational, concretely identifiable properties that make it possible to determine which journals meet a set of boundary conditions for Diamond OA journals that can be included in the Diamond Discovery Hub.

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Glossary

Open licence; persistent identifier

Keywords

Open Access (OA)

Licensing

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2.2 Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)

Abstract:

The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) is a cornerstone of the DIAMAS project. DOAS is focused on aligning quality and best practices across non-fee-based open access scholarly journals, more commonly known as Diamond OA. DOAS has been developed in different stages and derives from the Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP), a refined framework of quality standards that establishes a unified benchmark, prioritising quality, transparency, sustainability and equity. DOAS presents a two-level approach to compliance with its standards, distinguishing between required and desired elements. It meets a variety of institutional publishing demands, and contributes to enhancing the accessibility and quality of Diamond OA journals.

Main text:

The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) is a cornerstone of the DIAMAS project. DOAS is focused on aligning quality and best practices across non-fee-based open access scholarly journals, more commonly known as Diamond OA. DOAS has been developed in different stages and derives from the Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP), a refined framework of quality standards that establishes a unified benchmark, prioritising quality, transparency, sustainability and equity. DOAS presents a two-level approach to compliance with its standards, distinguishing between required and desired elements. It meets a variety of institutional publishing demands, and contributes to enhancing the accessibility and quality of Diamond OA journals. The ultimate mission of DOAS is the advancement of science and scholarship. The quality parameters it puts forward should be viewed as a public good.

DOAS aims at establishing a common quality standard for Diamond OA publishers based on seven core components, including funding, governance, and open science practices. Developed through an iterative refinement process, EQSIP V1.0 integrated relevant standards from 71 documents, followed by a gap analysis and EQSIP V2.0 further refined the structure and content of V1.0 based on the feedback and the recommendations of the gap analysis, and including the co-creative input from various publishing communities across Europe. Eight focus groups and a public consultation process were taken into account in finalising EQSIP V2.0, ensuring inclusivity and representativity. This collaborative effort allowed DOAS to evolve into a comprehensive standard for Diamond OA publishing in Europe and beyond, reflecting the diverse needs of Diamond OA publishers. The iterative approach adopted in its elaboration ensures DOAS's adaptability and provides a good representation of evolving scholarly publishing practices.

The seven core components of DOAS are:

1. Funding: This component aims at ensuring a sustainable Diamond OA business model, editorial independence, and cost transparency.

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2. Governance: The purpose of this component is to define and establish ownership and control by the scholarly community, transparent mission-driven strategic governance, and clear relations with service providers.
3. Open Science practices: This component promotes open science policies, authors' rights, intellectual property rights, licensing practices, and sharing via a repository.
4. Editorial management: This component emphasises the importance of strong independent editorial bodies, transparency in peer review, editorial quality processes, and research integrity.
5. Technical service efficiency: This component aims at ensuring strong publishing infrastructures, interoperability and metadata robustness, as well as appropriate collaboration and preservation strategies.
6. Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact: This component enhances the visibility, communication, dissemination, and impact of published content through indexing, communication through various channels, and the provision of comprehensive usage metrics.
7. Equity, diversity, inclusion, and belonging (EDIB), gender, and multilingualism: This component focuses on promoting EDIB policies and practices, and ensuring equal participation, accessibility, and multilingualism as key quality elements.

DOAS offers two levels of compliance with its standards, distinguishing between required and desired elements. The required elements are necessary to meet the quality standard, while the desired elements provide advanced recommendations aimed at further improving compliance with the quality standard. Through this framework, Diamond OA publishers can improve the quality and transparency of governance, processes and workflows in their journal publishing activities, ensuring a common standard of transparency, accessibility, and integrity in scholarly publishing practices across disciplines and regions. Ultimately, this effort to align publishing standards across Diamond OA publishers will benefit both the scholarly community and society at large.

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Glossary

Open Science

Keywords

Open access; Open science

Licensing

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2.3 Funding

Abstract:

The individual needs and options available for funding Diamond open access publishers are to a large extent influenced by contextual factors. Publishing services should be able to find a suitable and sustainable mix of funding sources that can be publicly disclosed and do not interfere with editorial decision-making. Recording the research funding information of published content in a structured way is an important dimension both for research integrity and compliance with funder requirements.

Main text:

A publishing model based on subscription provides a funding mechanism for most publishing organisations where access to journal content is conditional on paying a subscription or a read-and-publish agreement. Similarly, Gold OA publishers rely on income generated by Article Processing Charges (APCs) directed at the author, organisation or funder. Organisations engaging in Diamond OA publishing lack such a convenient funding mechanism, since access to the journals is not conditional on any fees for authors or readers. Diamond OA publications are often funded through a mix of various revenue streams for sustaining their operations, and direct monetary funding is used in combination with in-kind support (Bosman et al., 2021). Any funding available and viable for financing publication activities in one organisation might not be so for another. This highlights the need for a thorough mapping of resource needs and available options. Earlier projects have identified some of the available funding mechanisms and cost-

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cutting strategies that are relevant on the level of individual journals (Wise & Estelle, 2019) but the available knowledge at the organisational level is still very limited.

Diamond OA publishers are strongly dependent on their country of operation, the availability of existing technical infrastructure at their home institutions, and organisational factors. The public funding mechanisms available for publishing organisations in Europe vary considerably (Laakso & Multas, 2023). Many countries around the world have national or regional publication portals that provide the option of low or no-cost publishing from a purely technical perspective. This lowers the need to obtain additional funding for setting up and maintaining a Diamond OA publisher's technical environment. Where applicable, the relationship between Diamond OA publication outlets and their host institutions is crucial, since that is often a channel for funding (monetary and or in-kind) and other supporting resources.

Principles of transparency

Transparency on funding applies to the way the Diamond OA publishing service is funded, as well as to the funding information of scholarly publications published by that service.

A Diamond OA publisher should have a clearly stated policy that covers the implemented business model and compliance with funder and/or institutional or national OA policies (if applicable). Independently of the variety of funding streams, it is important that such information be declared on the website of the Diamond OA publishing services, as well as on the information pages of individual Diamond OA journals, to increase the financial transparency of the operations.

Transparency about the types of revenue streams and their destination should be provided. These may include donations, time-limited funds, Voluntary Author Contributions (VAC), or ongoing institutional support. If a Diamond OA publisher is open to external funding, explicit policies for accepting such funding should be provided. Editorial operations should be independent and free from influence from the bodies that financially support the publisher and its journals. If the Diamond OA publisher wishes to run advertising, there should be formal written policies for such advertising in both print and digital versions.

When it comes to managing the funding information relating to published research, consistent workflows should allow authors, editors and reviewers to disclose financial conflicts of interest (in the conflict of interest statement and the metadata) and openly state all sources of funding (in the funding acknowledgements/statements and the metadata).

Long term vision

It is recommended that Diamond OA publishers have a sustainability plan, i.e. a strategy for the medium-term economic viability, described on the website that also describes OA sustainability via cooperative work schemes and costs shared across actors. In terms of long-term stability, some of the most desirable funding is financial support from academic institutions and public

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organisations such as ministries or research funding agencies that have either performing research or funding it as their goal. Contributions should not be tied to individual outputs or groups of authors.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Ownership and Governance

Editorial Quality

Related Guidelines and training materials

Revenue streams

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Keywords

Funding; governance; sustainability; transparency

Licensing

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2.4 Ownership and governance

Abstract:

Diamond OA publishing is driven and owned by scholarly communities. This article outlines how that can be achieved in line with the Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024). Diamond OA Publishers must be (part of) a not-for-profit academic or scholarly organisation, and have legal ownership of journal and book titles. Publisher governance structures, interactions with service providers (SPs), and relations to its journals and books should be clearly indicated on the publisher's web page.

Main text:

Ownership

This article provides an outline of how scholar-driven ownership and governance of Diamond OA publishing can be achieved in line with the Diamond OA Standard (DOAS, Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024). Diamond OA Publishers must be (part of) a not-for-profit academic or scholarly organisation. These include but are not limited to research performing organisations (RPOs), research funding organisations (RFOs), organisations connected to RPOs (university libraries, university presses, faculties, and departments), research institutes, and scholarly societies. Publishers are expected to provide transparent information about their ownership structure on their web page.

Diamond OA publishers should have a defined policy about the ownership of the individual journals and books they publish. This policy includes the legal parameters governing the

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relationship between the publisher and its published journals and books, the determination of ownership for each title, and the explicit definition of the rights/duties afforded to editors within the Diamond OA publisher. It also includes details about the closure of individual journals, book series, and other outputs, as well as the transfer and preservation of their assets.

Diamond OA publishers retain legal ownership of individual journal titles. They must make efforts to avoid that ownership of individual journal titles can be transferred to commercial publishers. One way of achieving that is for the publisher to grant beneficial ownership of the journal to the editorial team and board of the individual journal. This establishes community ownership, empowers the journal's community, and makes it difficult to sell the journal. Such an arrangement has sometimes been called 'non-transferable ownership'. Community ownership of journal titles means that a Diamond OA publisher can easily change its service provider without changing the journal title, since ownership of the journal title always remains vested in the publisher and its community.

Governance

Three types of governance information should be distinguished:

- (a) the Diamond OA publishers own governance structure
- (b) the Diamond OA publishers relation with Service Providers
- (c) the Diamond OA publishers relation with the journals and book series it provides services for.

Diamond OA publishers offer information about both their strategic and internal governance structure on their web page. Strategic governance indicates how a particular Diamond OA publisher relates to its scholarly community stakeholders and its host institution; internal governance is about the way in which decisions are reached within the publisher, its governance model and organisation chart.

Diamond OA publishers have clear and potentially distinct policies about their relation with Service Providers (SPs). They may have commercial and non-commercial relations with various SPs that are responsible for distinct technical and non-technical aspects of the workflow (e.g. ownership of infrastructure, copy-editing and typesetting services used, etc.). Information about the various SPs the Diamond OA publisher works with will be provided on its web page.

Diamond OA publishers provide information about their relation with individual journals and book series, and this information is clearly indicated on the web page of the individual journals and book series. Individual journals and/or published books have a clear protocol to guide their relation with all their SPs. They must have one or more policies that apply to its journals and books for the selection of members of editorial bodies (editorial teams and boards) that should include details of their mandate's length, the regular renewal process, and clearly defined procedures for the dissolution of the board. All journals of the Diamond OA publisher must have a clear definition of the roles and responsibilities of the editorial board towards authors,

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reviewers, readers and the scientific community, journal and platform owners, the publisher, and the public.

Editors-in-chief and/or Editorial Teams must have full authority and responsibility over the entire editorial content of each journal published by the Diamond OA publisher and the publication timing of that content. Articles and books should carry a Creative Commons licence, preferably CC BY.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Funding

Editorial management

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

Implementing community-led governance in publishing services

Copyright, authors' rights policy

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For an example of governance and ownership of a Diamond OA journal title, see: <https://www.glossa-journal.org/site/governance/>

Keywords

Funding; governance; sustainability; transparency

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2.5 Open science practices

Abstract

In the current scholarly communication system, Diamond OA publishers are expected to be implementers and promoters of Open Science (OS). They need to be acquainted with OS principles, have them embedded in their policies, and ensure that their workflows are aligned with best practices and standards for facilitating and incentivising OS.

Main text

Open Science (OS) is fast becoming the default way for working on and communicating scholarly content today. Even though lately more emphasis is put on other scholarly outputs (like research data) and communication channels, the relevance of traditional publications (like journals, books or conference proceedings) remains, and it is important for all publishers and publishing service providers to adapt to the new landscape, and find ways to openly interact with other stakeholders.

Open access and open science policies

For each Diamond open access publisher, it is important that it possesses a thorough understanding of what OS is and what it entails. According to UNESCO (2021), it is “an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community”. The publisher needs to reflect on different aspects of OS (not just open access) that are of relevance to its publishing activities and services, reach decisions on outstanding issues, and clearly communicate its policies. The issues that need to be addressed by the policies include: authors’ rights, copyright and licensing, research data sharing and data availability, research protocols and methods sharing and publishing, open research software, open peer review, preprints, repository deposits, publication and sharing of negative scientific results and incentives and rewards. All policies should be publicly available on the publisher’s website.

In defining its policies on specific issues of open science, a Diamond OA publisher needs to consider and be aware of the policies of other related stakeholders: its parent institution, national and international governmental bodies or research funding organisations, and professional or disciplinary associations. Alignment with higher-level policies relevant to the publisher’s context is recommended, especially if it helps its authors comply with funders and institutional requirements.

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Authors' rights, copyright and licensing

Unlike traditional publishing, where the assignment of copyright to the publishers was common practice, within the OS framework a strong emphasis is put on authors retaining rights to their intellectual outputs, making them both openly available without delays and reusable under the terms of an open licence. Both, rights retention and the use of an open licence should not just provide content that is free to read, but true open access and reuse of knowledge for everyone (Labastida i Juan et al., 2023). Publishers should provide clear information to any user of the published content on the conditions of (re)use, in human and machine-readable form, on the article/chapter and publication level. Moreover, a Diamond OA publisher should provide clear information on its policy towards authors' rights, copyright and licensing. For journal publishers, the same information should be accurately reported in the relevant registries (such as [DOAJ](#) or [Sherpa Romeo](#)) and regularly updated.

Research data sharing and data availability policies

In the OS framework, research data have a dual role. It is acknowledged that research datasets have a value of their own, and Diamond OA publishers should encourage and enable the publication of datasets, their reuse, citation and crediting of their creators. In addition, the publishing system can greatly benefit from connecting the publications with the underlying data and making them available to editors, reviewers, and readers, to achieve greater transparency and reliability of published knowledge (Nosek et al., 2014). In their policies related to research data, Diamond OA publishers should follow best practices in providing guidance for data deposit and sharing, metadata description, data availability statements (including the valid reasons for exceptions from sharing), data citation and the use of persistent identifiers.

Publication and sharing of open research software, research protocols and methods, and negative scientific results

Opening up the process of scientific knowledge production can lead to greater efficiency of scientific work, transparency and regaining society's trust in science and scholarship. Diamond OA publishers have a major role in the opening of the scientific process, since they can define policies and introduce practices that foster publishing and making available the different outputs, protocols and methods as they are relevant to specific disciplinary, epistemic and methodological contexts. Whenever appropriate, early sharing and registering of the study designs and reporting on the negative results should be encouraged by publishers.

Open peer review

Open peer review is the preferred practice of OS. It aims to improve the reviewing system through a more collaborative mindset and opens up the complete scholarly discussion rather than just making accessible the results of that discussion. Diamond OA publishers will consider encouraging open reviewing policies that are in line with the [NISO Standard Terminology for Peer Review](#) (NISO MECA Working Group and Standing Committee, 2023). They should provide

D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite

reviewers with the possibility of: (a) signing their reviews either with their identity only visible to the editor, author, and the other reviewers, or with their identity visible to all readers; (b) publishing either review summaries or the full content of their review reports with identities visible or not, either alongside the published article or in an open preprint repository. Such policies can also allow the corresponding author to opt for publishing either review summaries or the full content of review reports of their article or chapter. In their efforts to introduce open peer review and choose the preferred type of it, IPs should listen carefully to research communities, set their open peer review goals, be pragmatic in approaching it, plan technologies and costs, further communicate the concept, and evaluate performance (Ross-Hellauer & Görögh, 2019).

Preprints and repository deposits

Diamond OA publishers should understand their role in the wider ecosystem of open scholarly communication, interact and collaborate with other actors such as repositories, preprint sharing services or data archives, and encourage, instead of preventing the free circulation of knowledge. They should accept the submissions of preprints that are already available, and allow the deposit of any version of the published work in open repositories of authors' choice, before or after the publication. If the publisher uses a CC BY licence, and/or if it has a policy where authors retain publishing rights, the right to deposit and share is already granted to the authors.

Incentives and rewards

Diamond OA publishers should be aware of recent efforts to reform the research assessment (e.g. [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#)) and facilitate it through their policies and practices. They should provide acknowledgements and make the publishing work of editors, reviewers and other contributors visible and recognisable. They should also apply standards that will enable easier tracking, monitoring, giving credit, and rewarding OS practices (primarily through describing them with quality metadata and using persistent identifiers). Using internationally standardised systems like the [CRedit](#) taxonomy (NISO, n.d.) for different contributor roles is a preferred practice.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Software and interoperability

Metadata

Research integrity

Preservation and content formats

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging ([EDIB](#))

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

Handling negative research results

Availability of research protocols, methods and software

Research data sharing policy

Preprints

D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite

Self-archiving policy

Use of open licenses in open access publishing

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Glossary

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Open Science

Persistent identifiers

Preprints

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

How can I incentivise, support and acknowledge open science practices among authors and reviewers?

Where can I find information and guidelines on the OS practices presented?

How can I link published content to supplementary materials deposited into an external infrastructure?

Keywords

Copyright; free and open-source software (FOSS); licensing; multilingualism; open access; open science; peer review; research data; research integrity; transparency

Licensing

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2.6 Editorial quality

Abstract

Evaluation procedures used by journals, often in the form of peer review, play an essential role in maintaining the quality, reliability, and validity of published contents. These procedures have a direct influence on shaping the nature and quality of a journal's editorial process. Therefore, this evaluation process must be rigorous and meet the basic standards as well as generally accepted practices within specific disciplines.

Main text

The landscape of scholarly publishing has seen a dramatic change over the last few decades due to digital innovation, with a pivotal transition to online and open access publishing. Open access journals have made academic research more accessible to a wider audience at a much faster speed. Evidence indicates that open access publications have increased significantly in recent years (STM, 2022). This has resulted in growing importance that scholarly research contained in those journals must be meticulously evaluated through a rigorous editorial process to ensure the overall quality of journal contents.

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The evaluation process conducted by the journal's editorial department is most often carried out via peer review. It is a fundamental part of scholarly publishing and acts as a function to prevent low quality and unreliable research from reaching the academic community. The specifics of how the peer review system works may vary across journals and disciplines. However, the journal must meet basic and general principles of peer review for achieving good publishing practice. As a minimum (Hames, 2016; COPE et al.):

1. The selection of peer reviewers should be carried out by the editorial team to ensure that reviewers are experts in the manuscript's subject area that do not have a conflict of interest with the author(s), and have the required expertise to validate research results and distinguish significant contributions.
2. The peer review policy on the journal's website should be as transparent as possible to clearly state the specific type and details of the review procedure.
3. The editorial decision should be made based on the scholarly merits of the submitted manuscript and should not be influenced by other factors such as the origin of the manuscript or business models.
4. All parties involved in the peer review process must declare any potential conflict of interest and avoid reviewing and handling manuscripts they are not suitable to make an objective and fair assessment.
5. The proportion of published articles contributed by members of the editorial team and board should be limited to 25% in any single issue, ensuring that the endogeneity of a journal is minimised and a more diversified authorship is encouraged.

The evaluation process of a journal can be organised at different stages of journal publishing, either before or after publication, and in other formats. No matter which review model is adopted, the journal or book publisher must openly commit to maintaining high standards in their editorial process since this has significant influence on the journal's or book publisher's reputation, their credibility, and the way in which they make a contribution to the academic community.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Editorial management

Research integrity

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

Basic editorial info that should be displayed

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Frequently asked questions (FAQ)

Do funding sources influence editorial decisions?

How can I manage conflicts of interest?

Keywords

Peer review; transparency

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2.7 Editorial management

Abstract

The number of scholarly journals has been increasing rapidly in recent years, and it is hard for users to ensure that sources are trustworthy. Publishers must provide information in the journal's website or on the website of the publisher (scholarly society) to prospective authors and readers so that they can identify relevant journals and easily view their editorial policies and procedures.

Main text

With the consistent increase in numbers of scholarly journals, it is essential for users to be able to select appropriate titles and trust that they are honest and reputable. This article highlights the importance for journals of providing clear and transparent information to prospective authors and readers, and of implementing best practices in publishing.

One of the first indicators for the user is the journal's aims and scope. This should be a clear definition of its objectives and subject coverage, and demonstrate the reason for its existence. This statement not only guides the editorial team, but it also communicates the focus of a journal or book publisher to potential readers and contributors, and enhances discoverability through

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search engines. Established journals should revisit their aims and scope regularly to ensure that they remain relevant and accurately reflect the current focus.

Publishers are expected to publish journal content according to a defined schedule, whether this is based on regular issues, or under a continuous publishing model. Journal managers must ensure that their publishing schedule is realistic rather than aspirational. Indexing services may not consider a journal for inclusion if it is not publishing on time.

The roles and responsibilities of the editorial team must be well-defined, including those of the editors, editorial board and internal staff. In general, the Editor-in-Chief and editorial board are recognised experts who will direct the journal strategy and development, as well as providing subject expertise in the research area of the journal. Consideration should be given to including a diverse range of editors who can act as ambassadors for the journal and reflect its quality. Details of the names and affiliations of members who have agreed to serve on the board must be published on the journal website.

Author guidelines define the criteria for inclusion of articles in the journal, including article types allowed, instructions for paper submission and layout, and any requirements specific to the journal. The guidelines should also include details of the journal's policies on open access licensing, copyright, author charges and publication ethics. These broad criteria are also applicable to book publishing.

Adherence to data protection rules is essential, and journals and book publishers must ensure their operations comply with the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR) and other relevant regulations.

An often neglected aspect of open access publishing is digital preservation. Publishers and journal managers are strongly recommended to implement a preservation strategy so that journal and book content is archived in case of data loss or service interruption. Low- or no-cost solutions are available that will enable journal and book content to be safely preserved for the future.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Editorial quality

Preservation and content formats

Research integrity

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

GDPR and personal data

References

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Keywords

GDPR; preservation; transparency

Glossary

General Data Protection Regulation

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2.8 Research integrity

Abstract

Research Integrity (RI) involves conducting ethical research to the highest standards. Core principles include reliability, honesty, care, and transparency. RI varies culturally and disciplinarily. Transparent practices include Open Access, proper data management, and adherence to ethical standards. Institutional responsibility, especially for Diamond OA publishers, is vital in promoting a culture of RI, providing training, and establishing policies to prevent and address research misconduct.

Main text

Research integrity (RI) is the commitment to conducting research ethically and in accordance with the highest standards of professionalism and rigour, as defined by organisations like Science Europe (2015). It involves upholding core values and principles that guide the responsible conduct of individuals involved in scientific research, including those who perform, finance, or evaluate it, as well as the institutions that publish and disseminate research.

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Adhering to principles, values, professional ethics, and standards ensures the quality of research by promoting honest, accurate, efficient, and objective reporting in publication and dissemination channels. This commitment enhances the reputation of science and fosters public trust, contributing significantly to societal advancements.

Fundamental principles of RI, outlined by organisations such as ALLEA (2023) and the Universities UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity (2023), include reliability and rigour in research performance, honesty in all aspects of research, care, respect, and fairness in interactions with various stakeholders, accountability throughout the research process, and transparency and openness in reporting methods and findings.

These values may vary across cultural, historical, national, political, and economic contexts. Other accepted principles encompass accuracy, efficiency, objectivity, impartiality, independence, openness, good research stewardship, and responsibility for future researchers.

RI also involves transparent practices and actions such as facilitating Open Access and Open Science, proper data management, scrutiny in drawing conclusions, authorship and contributorship statements, reproducibility, adherence to ethical, legal, and professional standards, promotion of equal opportunities and diversity, and compliance with best research and publishing practices.

RI's responsibility extends to the entire research community, including individual researchers, institutions, research funders, academies, learned societies, editors, publishers, and relevant bodies. Institutional policies, such as those of Diamond OA publishers, play a crucial role in fostering a culture of research integrity, promoting values like equity, diversity, and inclusion, and supporting infrastructure for the generation, management, and protection of research materials.

Diamond OA publishers support ethics and RI training to ensure that researchers and editors are well-versed in relevant codes and regulations and possess the necessary skills to apply them effectively. For this purpose, the wider scholarly community's resources, e.g., those offered by HEIs, academic libraries, departments/schools/and other Diamond OA publishers, can be used. Additionally, Diamond OA publishers should establish robust policies on research integrity to prevent and address misconduct at all stages of research, thereby upholding the quality of scientific publications and public trust in research findings.

Research misconduct, including fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, and other unethical actions, is explicitly outlined and regulated by publisher policies. This includes addressing conflicts of interest, misuse of seniority, manipulation of statistics, and various other actions that compromise the integrity of research. The Diamond OA publisher ensures that all its publications have clear policies making them available on its website:

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- Editorial policies and procedures are transparent and easily accessible
- Policies on research integrity and publication ethics, authorship and contributorship, complaints and appeals, data sharing, ethical oversight, intellectual property, post-publication discussions, corrections and retractions clearly stated
- Policy on chatbots and other writing assistance tools in line with industry best practices

This commitment contributes to maintaining the highest standards of research ethics within the scientific community.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Editorial management

Editorial quality

Open science practices

References

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Glossary

Research integrity
Research misconduct
Responsible research

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

What are my research integrity obligations as a member of the academic/research community?
Does my institution/founder/publisher have a policy on research integrity, research misconduct and/or responsible research?
Do funding sources influence editorial decisions?
How can I manage conflicts of interest?
When and how should I make a report of possible research misconduct?

Keywords

Open access; open science; research data; research integrity; transparency

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2.9 Software and interoperability

Abstract

In scholarly publishing, an ideal online publishing infrastructure should support workflows from manuscript submission, through peer review, to content display. Although building a fully professional platform is a challenge, institutional publishers and service providers can use a number of free and open-source software packages that offer out-of-the-box functionalities and make it possible to create an interoperable publishing venue.

Main text

In scholarly publishing, an ideal online publishing infrastructure should support publishing workflows from manuscript submission, through peer review, to content display. Such a platform makes it easier for publishers to handle documentation – manuscripts, reviews and correspondence – and to archive what needs to be preserved, preventing data and documentation loss in case of major changes in the editorial team. It also makes it possible to display the information about the publisher and their published outputs, as well as to feature each article or chapter on a dedicated landing page and enable straightforward and easy searching and navigation between articles or chapters and their source publications (journals or books) via a table of contents, menus and links.

Along with displaying content for human readers, the publishing platform should be able to display the metadata describing publications and their subunits in line with widely adopted metadata schemas (e.g. [Dublin Core](#), [DataCite](#), [Crossref](#), [JATS XML](#) for journals / [ONIX](#), MARC for books, etc.), via standard protocols for metadata exchange ([Open Access Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting – OAI-PMH](#), [REST API](#), HTTPS, etc.), so that general search engines (e.g. Google, Google Scholar) and academic aggregators (e.g. [OpenAIRE](#), [CORE](#), [BASE](#)) can access, process and disseminate their metadata. Publishing platforms should also support massive metadata export (as CSV files, ONIX XML feeds or in any other established format) and provide metadata records to libraries (e.g. MARC).

Building a fully professional publishing platform that has all these functionalities from scratch may seem an unattainable goal. However, thanks to the availability of free and open-source (FOSS) solutions, such as [Open Journal Systems](#), [Janeway](#), [Kotahi](#), [PubSweet](#) for journals (Lutz et al., 2023), and [Open Monograph Press](#), [PubPub](#), Manifold, Fulcrum, Scalar, etc. for books (Adema et al., 2022), institutional publishers and service providers are able to establish fully functional publishing platforms enabling them to carry out editorial and publishing workflows according to high professional standards and best practices (Baker, 2020). Not only do the mentioned solutions offer out-of-the-box functionalities that can fairly easily be enriched with free add-ons, but they are also designed and maintained by non-profit organisations and communities who seek to provide sufficient documentation and support knowledge exchange through forum discussions. Keeping this in mind, institutional publishers and service providers

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should contribute to the community efforts whenever possible, by sharing the code of any new add-ons they may have developed.

To support Diamond OA, in some countries shared infrastructures based on free and open-source software are maintained at the national level and offered to institutional publishers on the software-as-a-service basis free of charge (e.g. [HRCAK](#) in Croatia, [ePublishing EKT](#) in Greece, [Openjournals.nl](#) in the Netherlands, [PubIN](#) in Portugal, [Recyt](#) in Spain, [Online Scholarly Journals](#) in Finland etc.).

The publishing platform should conform to current interoperability standards ([OpenAIRE Guidelines](#), [KBART](#), [COUNTER](#)), accessibility guidelines (e.g. [W3C Web Content Accessibility Guidelines – WCAG](#)) and open science principles, and it should be regularly updated and backed up. Publishers should strive to use free and open-source software as much as possible in their editorial and publishing workflows (Maxwell et al., 2019). Technical interoperability should be supported by appropriate policies allowing metadata distribution under the Creative Commons CC0 Public Domain Dedication licence and text and data mining (automatic downloading, extraction and indexing of the full texts and the associated metadata).

Related Toolsuite Articles

Metadata

Content formats and preservation

Open Science Practices

Equity, Diversity and Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)

Visibility, Indexation, Communication, Marketing and Impact

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Glossary

File format
Free and open-source software
Interoperability
Metadata

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

What are the basic functionalities that a publishing infrastructure should have [do publishing infrastructures support copyediting and layout workflows]?

How can I assign persistent identifiers to published content?

What are the common metadata formats used for exporting publication metadata?

What are the standard protocols for retrieving metadata from publishing infrastructures?

What are the main open source publishing infrastructures?

What are the best practices for documenting and preserving content and metadata over time?

What are the main services that support content preservation?

Keywords

Accessibility; free and open-source software (FOSS); indexing / indexation; interoperability; metadata; open science; research data; research integrity; transparency

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2.10 Metadata

Abstract

Metadata are crucial for the discoverability and dissemination of published outputs. To make sure that their content will be indexed by search engines, aggregators and other services, and that it will reach the intended audience, publishers and service providers should follow a set of standards and guidelines determining how metadata should be structured, curated and distributed.

Main text

In the context of open access scholarly publishing, metadata are digital pieces of information that describe published outputs (articles, books, journals, etc.). Metadata are normally structured according to a metadata model that relies on a metadata standard. This ensures that the information provided is meaningful for both humans and machines and sufficient for an unambiguous identification of published outputs. (Avanço, 2023a; 2023b)

The most common metadata for published outputs include:

- Title(s)(of an article / contribution and of the source publication).
- Full names and institutional affiliations of authors.
- Abstracts.
- Keywords (controlled or free-text).
- Publisher name.
- Publication date.
- International standard numbers (ISSN, eISSN, ISBN, ISMN etc.).
- Persistent identifiers for the publication ([DOI](#)), authors and contributors ([ORCID](#)), author affiliations ([ROR](#)), and funding organisations ([ROR](#)), as well as other relevant persistent identifiers.

Metadata can also include author roles (e.g. according to the [CRediT](#) taxonomy), funding information (e.g. the name of the funder and the grant ID), copyright and licensing information, conflict-of-interest statements and bibliographic references. In case of journal articles or book chapters, metadata can include volume or issue information and pagination.

Standard numbers and persistent identifiers (PIDs) for publications are particularly helpful in identifying published outputs because they are registered in curated registries, along with other metadata describing a publication. Thanks to this, it is possible to retrieve other relevant metadata based on standard numbers or PIDs. For example, if a DOI is known, it will be possible to retrieve the type of publication, its title, publisher and the publication date, ISSN and journal title, if this is a journal article, etc.

D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite

When displaying metadata on online publishing platforms, publishers should make it easy for users to find relevant information about a specific output (e.g. journal article) on a single page, without having to search for it elsewhere. To achieve this, following general search engines such as Google's recommendations, each published item (article, chapter, book, etc.) should have a dedicated landing page (with a unique URL) showing the above-mentioned metadata and a link to the full text.

Along with making this information available to human users, publishers should ensure that it is also accessible to various search engines and aggregators, which can increase the visibility and use of the published content. Search engines and aggregators require that metadata be exposed in a specific format (e.g. XML, JSON, HTML, CSV) via an appropriate metadata exchange protocol ([Open Access Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting – OAI-PMH](#), [REST API](#), HTTPS, etc.). Furthermore, machine-readable metadata are also relevant for human users who want to export them for analysis or import them in reference managers.

Metadata should also be included in the full text in human and machine-readable formats (e.g. embedded in PDF or in [JATS XML](#)).

Setting up machine-readable metadata requires technical expertise but, fortunately, publishers do not have to do everything from scratch, as free and open-source software solutions are available. Platforms such as [Open Journal Systems](#) or [Janeway](#) come with ready-made solutions for displaying metadata on landing pages for humans and exposing them for machines in several formats. For books, a similar approach is being implemented by the open-source and community-led metadata management system [Thoth Open Metadata](#).

Apart from ensuring that technical requirements for metadata sharing are met, publishers should also enable the seamless flow of metadata by releasing them in the public domain (e.g. by using the Creative Commons CC0 Public Domain Dedication licence). By doing this, they enable various aggregators to harvest and disseminate their metadata without having to ask permission or deal with complicated licensing issues. Public-domain metadata play the key role in building non-commercial discovery platforms (e.g. [OpenAIRE Explore](#), [GoTriple](#), [OpenAlex](#)) and citation indexes (Peroni & Shotton, 2020). This is yet another reason why publishers should always deposit complete metadata about publications, including bibliographic references, with a registration agency (e.g. [CrossRef](#), [DataCite](#)) in line with the recommendations of the [Initiative for Open Citations \(I4OC\)](#) and [Initiative for Open Abstracts \(I4OA\)](#).

Related Toolsuite Articles

Software and interoperability

Content formats and preservation

Open Science Practices

Visibility, Indexation, Communication, Marketing and Impact

D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

Metadata formats and export, identifiers, CRediT tags, bibliographic references, JATS XML or equivalent

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Further reading

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Glossary

File formats

Interoperability

Metadata

Metadata exchange protocol

Metadata standard

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

What are the basic functionalities that a publishing infrastructure should have?

How can I assign persistent identifiers to published content?

What are the common metadata formats used for exporting publication metadata?

What are the standard protocols for retrieving metadata from publishing infrastructures?

What are the best practices for documenting and preserving content and metadata over time?

Keywords

Indexing/indexation; interoperability; metadata; metadata and file formats; persistent identifiers

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2.11 Preservation and content formats

Abstract

Digital preservation enables seamless access to content in case it becomes unavailable on the publisher's platform. As this is a major challenge in non-profit open access publishing, several community-led initiatives have been launched to support publishers. To facilitate preservation, interoperability and accessibility, publishers should rely on open standards when choosing file formats.

Main text

In the pre-digital age, the preservation of publications was ensured through libraries: by legal deposit, or by distributing physical copies to many libraries. Similar approaches are used in the digital age: legal deposit is extended to digital publications, whereas digital preservation

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services rely on copies preserved on a distributed network of servers, as indicated by the names of two widely used services: Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe ([LOCKSS](#)) and [CLOCKSS](#) (Controlled LOCKSS). LOCKSS and CLOCKSS, as well as another notable service, [Portico](#), are so-called 'dark archives', backup databases of born-digital or digitised content, hosted on multiple secured servers, which preserve the authentic original version of the content. In case the content becomes unavailable on the publisher's platform, these preservation services can deliver it to users, ensuring seamless access (Digital Preservation Coalition, 2015; Shah & Gul, 2019).

Although preservation should have a high priority in scholarly publishing, there are still many publishers who fail to ensure digital preservation for their outputs (Laakso, Matthias, & Jahn 2021). One of the reasons for this are the costs of the service. Several recent initiatives provide support to open access publishers, who are particularly vulnerable when it comes to digital preservation: the [PKP Preservation Network](#) (Sprout & Jordan, 2018) offers support to publishers using [Open Journal Systems](#) software, project [JASPER \(JournAIS are Preserved forevER\)](#) focuses on Diamond OA journals indexed in the [Directory of Open Access Journals](#), and the [Thoth Archiving Network](#) is a community initiative that seeks to help small and scholar-led book publishers (Cole, Barnes & Steiner, 2023).

One of the functionalities of digital preservation services is that they can ensure format conversion, in case the file formats used by the publisher become obsolete. This is one of the reasons why publishers should use open and well-documented file formats with a solid user base, which are more likely to get migration support in case of obsolescence.

Most publications are still provided in the camera-ready PDF format. However, this is not convenient for reading on small screens, nor is it optimal for searching and text and data mining. Tagging full-text content in the XML JATS or equivalent (e.g. TEI) format significantly improves machine readability and interoperability. Providing content in multiple digital formats (PDF, HTML, XML, ePub, etc.) improves user experience and content usability on various devices and browsers.

The fonts used on the publishing platform and in the full text should support Unicode and be open-source, suitable for cross-platform use and accessible. Images should be in high resolution, accompanied with descriptive captions, whereas tables should be well-constructed, annotated and easy to read and interpret. Links to data, code, and other research outputs that underlie the publications and are available in external repositories should be provided both on the outputs' landing pages and in the full text.

Machine readable metadata exposed through metadata exchange protocols and on outputs' landing pages should be provided in widely used formats that are also suitable for digital preservation (e.g. XML, CSV).

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Related Toolsuite Articles

Software and interoperability

Metadata

Open Science Practices

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB)

Visibility, Indexation, Communication, Marketing and Impact

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Glossary

File format

Metadata

Metadata exchange protocol

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

What are the best practices for documenting and preserving content and metadata over time?

Keywords

Accessibility; indexing/indexation; interoperability; metadata; metadata and content formats; preservation

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2.12 Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact

Abstract

Deliberate strategies to increase visibility can help published content be disseminated as widely as possible. These include traditional marketing activities by the publisher, also supported by social media usage and other communications activities by the authors including in multiple languages. Technical aspects such as indexation, search engine optimisation and use of good metadata can all contribute to making sure content reaches the intended audience.

Main text

The full potential of open access is achieved when content is disseminated as widely as possible to academia and society at large. This relates to both communication and marketing of the content itself via a broad range of channels, as well as maximising technical aspects of metadata and of search engine optimisation, for example.

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Newsletters, blogs, direct emails, mailing lists, content alerts, notifications, and RSS/Atom feeds are all useful mechanisms for publicising information. Marketing is key to ensuring that publications are viewed by their intended audiences and that activities are aligned with higher level strategic and operational goals (Schilan et al., 2021; Open Book Collective, 2023a).

Active use and regular updates of social media or social networking can also help to reach out to academia and society. Together with the use of traditional and modern dissemination methods, this can improve communication with a much broader audience. However, it is important for publishers to make sure that information provided on websites remains up-to-date in order to avoid misinterpretation and misinformation, and that any direct marketing activities are carefully targeted and carried out responsibly, in particular when soliciting content and contacting prospective authors.

Visibility of publications themselves can be maximised in search engines and aggregators by using search engine optimisation techniques (Jisc, 2021), such as by providing structured metadata and XML sitemaps, by implementing metadata exchange protocols (e.g. OAI-PMH), or by enabling APIs. It is important to make sure that good metadata is in place from the start (PKP, n.d.).

Discovery services, aggregator databases, abstracting and indexing databases, and citation indexes can all help with content visibility, particularly when these are specific services relevant for the target audiences (OAPEN, 2022; Open Book Collective, 2023b). A journal index is a collection of journal titles, categorised by discipline, subject, publication type, or other features. Indexing can play a crucial role in enhancing the discoverability of journal articles. However there are noted limitations in the use of journal metrics (Nobes et al. 2023; Foxall et al. 2023). It is also helpful to encourage authors directly to make the published content available in open repositories and sharing services in order to increase its visibility.

Impact statements or simple (multi)language summaries can bring the content of scholarly publications closer to the general audience when added alongside published content. It is also recommended to provide translations of publications potentially interesting for non-academic audiences to the local language or, at least, to summarise their results in blog posts, social media posts and the like.

Post-publication reviews or online comments can further boost interest in content by a wider audience. Organising events like book promotions, journal promotions, the launching of a new journal issue, or working with the media (such as by issuing press releases) can help reach broader sectors of society.

Finally, metric indicators are an important source of information about content usage. A comprehensive array of indicators can be employed from article/chapter-level metrics (such as visits, views, downloads, citations), to altmetrics indicators and measurements or the geographical spread of visitors. Analytics software and methods can be used to generate and

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collect metrics. Good examples are Matomo and Plausible which are open source and GDPR-compliant.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Software and interoperability

Metadata

Preservation and content formats

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

Marketing, communication, and visibility

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Glossary

Article level metrics

Indexing / indexation

Metadata

Search engine optimisation

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

What can I do to increase the visibility of my publications?

What can help published content have a greater impact?

What metrics should I be aware of?

Keywords

Indexing/indexation; interoperability; metadata; multilingualism; visibility

Licensing

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2.13 Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)

Abstract

Historical practices have led to discrimination in scholarly publishing, harming individuals as well as research and society more broadly. Actors across the industry can take steps to promote equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB), e.g. by setting gender diversity goals and monitoring their progress, supporting multilingualism, and creating products accessible to all.

Main text

There is a growing recognition that some established practices in scholarly publishing have led to various types of discrimination, such as excluding certain groups from roles in the publishing process (le Roux, 2015). For example, women may have their manuscripts rejected more often than men, or may receive fewer invitations to serve as peer reviewers or journal editors. Similar

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exclusions may arise for other groups, such as speakers of languages other than English, scholars with disabilities, scholars of different races and ethnicities, or those from developing countries or less prestigious institutions. Adding to the problem, the effects of various types of disadvantages can be intersectional and cumulative (Kozlowski et al., 2022). For instance, a scholar who identifies as a Black, non-Anglophone, disabled woman can be marginalised on multiple fronts.

Some discrimination may stem from implicit or unconscious bias, but the results are often still harmful. Researchers who experience publishing-related discrimination may suffer career setbacks because they are perceived to be less productive or less prominent than members of more privileged groups (Amano et al., 2023). However, the impact does not end here. The low number of diverse voices may result in scholars from more privileged groups dominating research conversations and, as a consequence, perpetuating their own values while giving less space to differing viewpoints. Research as a whole can suffer because certain subjects or perspectives are overlooked or excluded, while societal benefits could be unevenly distributed since the results produced by this relatively homogeneous research group may not be equally pertinent to or accessible across all populations, regions and sectors (Sugimoto et al., 2019).

To dismantle discrimination in scholarly publishing, Diamond OA publishers should implement measures to address various facets of EDIB, such as gender diversity, linguistic diversity, and accessibility.

- **Equity:** Removing systemic barriers and biases to enable everyone to have equal opportunities.
- **Diversity:** Ensuring that people of different sexes, genders, abilities, career stages, races, ethnicities, geographic and institutional locations, and linguistic and cultural backgrounds are represented in the community.
- **Inclusion:** Ensuring that all individuals are visible, heard and considered.
- **Belonging:** Treating everyone as a full member of the community and helping them to thrive.

Different actors in the scholarly publishing ecosystem, including authors, peer reviewers, editors, editorial board members, librarians, and Diamond OA publishers, can play a role. Examples of actions to be taken include adopting inclusive language; developing and sharing diversity statements, action plans, and policies for EDIB; setting goals for and assessing and monitoring progress in EDIB; implementing inclusive and accessible websites, content and metadata; and promoting multilingualism in scholarly publishing.

Providing guidance for implementing EDIB measures across the whole scholarly publishing community is challenging because some issues may differ from one location to another (e.g., cultural understanding of race and ethnicity differs by country). Nonetheless, this section of the tool suite seeks to raise awareness about the overall importance of addressing EDIB, to

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encourage critical reflection on ways to improve both collectively and within individual organisations, and to provide concrete pointers to get started.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata

Gender diversity

Multilingualism

Ownership and governance

Open science practices

Software and interoperability

Visibility, including indexation, communication, marketing and impact

Preservation and content formats

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Glossary

Accessibility

Accessibility policy

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging

Gender diversity

Multilingualism

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

What do equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB) mean in scholarly publishing?

What types of bias can occur in scholarly publishing?

What are some of the consequences of bias in scholarly publishing?

Who is responsible for ensuring EDIB in scholarly publishing?

What types of actions can be taken to improve EDIB in scholarly publishing?

Keywords

Accessibility; diversity, equity; inclusion; multilingualism

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2.14 Gender diversity

Abstract

In scholarly publishing, men are overrepresented as research subjects, authors, reviewers, editors, and executives. Steps to increase gender diversity can include actively recruiting more women and gender minorities to serve as reviewers, editors, and publishing executives,

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adopting policies to support gender-related reporting and double- or triple-anonymous reviewing, and offering guidance to reduce unconscious bias.

Main text

In scholarly publishing, gender diversity is understood as the equitable or fair representation of people of different genders (including men, women, non-binary individuals, and others) in various roles. It is relevant to multiple facets of scholarly publishing, and lack of gender diversity can have consequences for individuals, as well as for research and society more broadly. Although recent literature reports on gender disparities affecting women, less data is available on other groups (e.g. non-binary individuals) because it may not be collected, but also because they may not wish to disclose their gender, and their right to privacy must be respected.

Problems stemming from lack of gender diversity can begin early in research. For instance, if there is inadequate representation of genders in a study sample, the results could be less useful overall, while the absence of gender-related reporting could hinder the translation of research into practice (e.g., for healthcare). Diamond OA publishers can help by implementing policies that require gender-related reporting in journal publications (Sugimoto et al., 2019).

The degree and nature of gender diversity can differ greatly from one discipline to the next, (e.g. more men publish in engineering and more women in nursing). Nonetheless, across a range of disciplines and regions, it has been observed that women are underrepresented as authors, and particularly in prestigious authorship positions such as first, last or corresponding author (Sebo & Schwarz, 2023). Moreover, articles authored by women are cited less often (Chatterjee & Werner, 2021). There are encouraging signs that the gender gap for authorship and citations is beginning to shrink in some disciplines (Nature Aging, 2022; Ioannidis et al., 2023), but there is still work to be done, and some reports suggest that the COVID-19 pandemic caused a setback (Squazzoni et al., 2021). In part, their perceived lack of productivity and expertise results in fewer women in senior ranks and in prestigious positions (e.g., journal editors). One reason for the underrepresentation of women authors may be that reviewer pools and editorial boards also contain a majority of men, who may exhibit unconscious bias towards women, leading to a higher manuscript rejection rate (Fox & Paine, 2019). Diamond OA publishers can help to break the cycle by setting diversity goals for peer reviewers, editors and editorial boards and monitoring progress toward them. They can also adopt policies to mitigate the impact of bias, such as double-anonymous reviewing (i.e., where authors and reviewers are not known to one another) or triple-anonymous reviewing (i.e., where authors, reviewers, and editors are not known to one another) (Kern-Goldberger, 2022). While some other approaches, such as open reviews, may help to promote positive aspects such as transparency, there is a risk that unconscious bias could still play a role and be detrimental to gender minorities. Therefore, benefits of open reviews must be weighed carefully against potential for negative impacts for diversity (Helmer et al., 2017).

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Ultimately, a diverse editorial board will help Diamond OA publishers to create more inclusive peer review processes and to publish content by authors with diverse profiles.

Another way in which gender disparity can manifest itself in scholarly publishing is when fewer women are awarded leadership or executive roles within publishers (Li & Zhao, 2023). Finally, gender disparity may co-occur with or be exacerbated by other forms of discrimination, creating a problem of intersectionality. For instance, gender disparities may be even more pronounced in certain regions (e.g., low-income countries) (Morgan et al., 2019). To combat such problems, Diamond OA publishers can raise awareness about unconscious bias and offer training or guidance to their staff, editors, editorial boards, peer reviewers, and authors. Diamond OA publishers' leaders can also engage in self-reflection and take direct action to address gender disparities within their own organisations.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

Gender diversity

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Glossary

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)

Gender diversity

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

What do equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB) mean in scholarly publishing?

What types of bias can occur in scholarly publishing?

What are some of the consequences of bias in scholarly publishing?

Who is responsible for ensuring EDIB in scholarly publishing?

What types of actions can be taken to improve EDIB in scholarly publishing?

Keywords

Diversity; equity; inclusion

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2.15 Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata

Abstract

Accessibility ensures that people with disabilities can access content, metadata, and digital functionality on websites and in digital publications, while the use of inclusive language and images helps to ensure that diverse groups feel respected. Awareness of accessibility and inclusion is the first step, enabling Diamond OA publishers to subsequently develop policies and workflows that respect relevant regulations and improve user experience for all.

Main text

Accessibility refers to designing products or services to ensure that both content and digital functionality are available to everyone, regardless of abilities or impairments. Accessible designs ensure both direct access (i.e., unassisted) and indirect access (i.e., compatible with assistive technology such as screen readers). Meanwhile, inclusion involves proactively creating an environment where people feel welcomed, respected, and valued. When accessibility and inclusion are not taken into consideration by Diamond OA publishers, some users may be unable to access their products or services, or may feel uncomfortable doing so. In some cases, the publishers may even be non-compliant with relevant regulations.

A first step toward accessibility is awareness of the need to make content and functionality (e.g., on websites or in digital publications) accessible to everyone. Different regions have different requirements, so each Diamond OA publisher must investigate the legislation and recommendations for their region (W3C, 2023a). In a global context, a good strategy for increasing international accessibility compliance is to follow the [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines \(WCAG\) 2.2](https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidance/wcag/) (W3C, 2023b) and [Article 9](https://www.un.org/en/convention-rights-disabilities/) of the United Nations' Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UN, 2006).

Points to consider regarding accessibility in scholarly publishing include presenting text in a logical reading order; ensuring that font, colour, size, and line spacing are adjustable; separating presentation and content; providing image descriptions and alt-text for pictures and captions or transcripts for videos; including page numbers; and using metadata to communicate accessibility modes and features of resources. Many aspects of accessibility are specialised, and Diamond OA publishers can support accessibility by ensuring that they have staff with

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appropriate expertise. In addition, they can develop relevant accessibility statements and policies, and they can ensure that accessibility is built into their workflow as a strategic and operational priority and not treated as an afterthought or a one-off activity (Conrad & Kasdorf 2018).

Language choices can support both accessibility and inclusion in scholarly publishing. For instance, plain language summaries can make content accessible to non-specialist audiences and readers with lower literacy or using a non-dominant language, and Diamond OA publishers can publish these summaries alongside journal articles (Rosenberg et al., 2023). With regard to inclusivity, using respectful language is key (Ashwell et al., 2023). Inclusive language acknowledges diversity, conveys respect to all people, is sensitive to differences, and promotes equal opportunities. When writing, it is important not to simply adopt the point of view that represents whatever group is considered to be the default group. For instance, because scholarly publishing is currently dominated by English, it can be easy to default to framing communications from a Western viewpoint. This can also apply to other groups that have traditionally held more power, such as men, White people, or able-bodied people. Looking beyond text, it is important to use inclusive images and data visualisation techniques as well. Diamond OA publishers can promote inclusivity by using respectful language and diverse images on their websites and in their resources, and by adopting policies that encourage authors, peer reviewers and editors to do the same. Moreover, they can provide these groups with some guidance or training resources about how to implement inclusive language and images.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

Accessible/inclusive website content and metadata

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Glossary

Accessibility

Accessibility policy

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

What do equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB) mean in scholarly publishing?

What types of bias can occur in scholarly publishing?

What are some of the consequences of bias in scholarly publishing?

Who is responsible for ensuring EDIB in scholarly publishing?

What types of actions can be taken to improve EDIB in scholarly publishing?

Keywords

Accessibility; inclusion; indexing/indexation; metadata

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2.16 Multilingualism

Abstract

English dominates scholarly publishing, but using a single language has consequences for researchers, scholarship and society. Multilingualism is the use of more than one language to disseminate research. This could include translating individual publications, but it also entails a publishing ecosystem where publishing takes place in a variety of languages. Steps to support multilingualism include diversifying reviewer pools and editorial boards, translating websites and resources, and implementing policies to publish in multiple languages.

Main text

In recent decades, English has emerged as the dominant language for scholarly publishing. However, using a single language for research dissemination privileges some scholars while marginalising others, which has consequences not only for individuals but for research and society more broadly. For instance, Non-Anglophone researchers may need longer to read and write in English and may face more revisions and rejections. This may result in a lower volume of research output, which could impact career advancement (Ramírez-Castañeda, 2020). What's more, when scholars do choose to publish in a language other than English, their work is less likely to be indexed in prestigious databases, thus making it less discoverable and less likely to be cited (Di Bitetti & Ferreras, 2017).

Meanwhile, English-speaking scholars, who come mainly from Western cultures, will have more visibility and power, and this could influence which subjects are investigated and which communities benefit from the results (Amano et al., 2016). Their higher visibility and volume of output may also improve career advancement opportunities for English speakers, such as prestigious appointments as journal editors, among others.

As the consequences of using a single language for research dissemination become clearer, the movement to make scholarly publishing multilingual is gaining momentum (e.g. Helsinki Initiative, 2019; UNESCO, 2021). In this context, multilingualism could include translating individual publications into more than one language, but it also means supporting publication in a variety of languages even when the works published are not translations of one another (e.g., one journal or article may be published in Finnish and another in Polish).

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Diamond OA publishers can help to support multilingual scholarly publishing in a variety of ways:

- Develop or revise a book publisher's or a journal's mission statements and objectives to improve linguistic diversity and monitor progress towards this goal.
- Translate book or journal websites and resources, as well as calls for papers, into languages beyond English.
- Diversify the pools of reviewers, editorial board members and editors to have greater linguistic coverage, and ask authors whether they can accept peer review or editorial feedback in other languages.
- Audit author guidelines to clarify policies and practices around multilingualism (e.g., which publishing languages are accepted, whether translations are permitted, how to cite works in other languages, whether total word limits can be extended for some languages).
- Provide concrete guidance to help authors write in a way that optimises their text for translation.
- Implement policies to host translated abstracts, plain language summaries or full-texts alongside published articles.
- Create a visible byline or a field in service acknowledgement platforms (e.g., Publons) to recognize translators or multilingual editors.
- Offer low-cost licence agreements that permit authors to translate their publications elsewhere or to publish translations of previously published manuscripts.
- Provide or facilitate translation support alongside editing support.
- Integrate new functionalities into journal platforms, such as the capacity to manage multilingual metadata, or a forum to facilitate peer language translation.
- Support metrics that allow non-English articles or journals to be cited more easily and equitably.

Related Toolsuite Articles

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)

Related Guidelines and Training Materials

Multilingualism

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Glossary

Multilingualism

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

What do equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB) mean in scholarly publishing?

What types of bias can occur in scholarly publishing?

What are some of the consequences of bias in scholarly publishing?

Who is responsible for ensuring EDIB in scholarly publishing?

What types of actions can be taken to improve EDIB in scholarly publishing?

Keywords

Accessibility; diversity; equity; inclusion; metadata; multilingualism; visibility

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2.17 Frequently Asked Questions

Open Science practices

1. How can I incentivise, support and acknowledge open science practices among authors and reviewers?

Publishers have a crucial role in incentivising, supporting and acknowledging Open Science (OS) practices among authors and reviewers. They can do so in at least three important ways:

- a) They can adapt their policies and submission workflows in a way that allows or even requires certain OS practices. For instance, they can accept submissions previously available as preprints, they can require data availability statements and data sharing whenever it is possible, they can leave copyright with the authors and publish content under open licences to enable reuse, they can ask for open reviews, they can be explicit in accepting submissions presenting the negative research results and so forth
- b) They can adapt their publishing platforms and technical infrastructures in a way that is compatible with OS. For instance, they can disseminate all the metadata, including the references, under the CC0, they can enable the process of open peer review, and they need to enable linking the research data when they are available
- c) They can provide some acknowledging mechanisms to enable crediting OS practices among authors and reviewers. Such mechanisms could be: citing the research data and other research outputs besides publications, providing structured information about authors' roles and contributions, using persistent identifiers for persons, outputs, institutions and funders, providing interoperable information about reviewers so they can be credited for their work.

2. Where can I find information and guidelines on the OS practices presented?

DIAMAS guidelines that describe the relevant OS practices are:

- Copyright, authors' rights policy
- Use of open licences in open access publishing
- Research data sharing policy
- Preprints
- Self-archiving policy
- Handling negative research results
- Availability of research protocols, methods and software

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- Metadata formats and export, identifiers, CRediT tags, bibliographic references, JATS XML or equivalent
- Multilingualism

3. How can I link published content to supplementary materials deposited into an external infrastructure?

The supplementary materials deposited in external platforms or infrastructures should always be linked via persistent identifiers (PIDs) and accompanied by textual citation or acknowledgement. The PIDs that are most often used for objects such as supplementary materials are DOIs, handles or URN-NBNs.

Editorial management, editorial quality and research integrity

1. What are my research integrity obligations as a member of the academic/research community?

As a member of the academic community, research integrity obligations include:

- **Honesty:** Ensuring the accuracy of research findings and being honest in all aspects of research
- **Transparency:** Sharing data, methodologies, and findings openly
- **Accountability:** Taking responsibility for research and its impacts
- **Ethical conduct:** Following ethical guidelines in the treatment of research subjects and data
- **Avoiding Misconduct:** Refraining from practices such as fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism.

2. Does my institution/founder/publisher have a policy on research integrity, research misconduct and/or responsible research?

Institutions, funders, and publishers typically have policies that cover:

- **Authorship and Contributorship:** Clear guidelines on who qualifies as an author and what constitutes a contribution
- **Handling Complaints and Appeals:** Procedures for addressing issues and appeals.
- **Conflicts of Interest:** Policies requiring disclosure of any potential conflicts
- **Data Sharing and Reproducibility:** Expectations for making data available and ensuring reproducibility
- **Ethical Oversight:** Oversight mechanisms for ethical conduct in research.

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3. Do funding sources influence editorial decisions?

Funding sources should not influence editorial decisions. Editorial independence is a critical aspect of research integrity. However, it is essential to disclose funding sources and any potential conflicts of interest to maintain transparency and trust.

4. How can I manage conflicts of interest?

To manage conflicts of interest:

- Disclosure: Always disclose any personal, financial, or professional conflicts that could influence your research
- Editorial Policies: Adhere to the editorial policies of journals regarding conflicts of interest
- Recusal: From the review process or decision-making in cases where a conflict exists
- Transparency: Ensure all conflicts are transparently communicated in publications and peer review processes.

5. When and how should I make a report of possible research misconduct?

Possible research misconduct should be reported when:

- There is evidence: Credible evidence of misconduct such as fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism
- Following Institutional Guidelines: Follow the procedures outlined by the host institution or publisher. Typically, this involves reporting to a designated research integrity officer or committee.

These references provide a framework for understanding and maintaining research integrity within the academic community:

Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing
<https://publicationethics.org/node/19881>

Open Access Journals Toolkit: <https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/>

Technical Service Efficiency

1. What are the basic functionalities that a publishing infrastructure should have [do publishing infrastructures support copyediting and layout workflows]?

An online publishing infrastructure should make it possible to:

- Display the information about the publisher and their published outputs

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- Feature each article or chapter on a dedicated landing page
- Enable easy content search and navigation.

The publishing platform should be able to display the metadata describing publications and their subunits in line with widely adopted metadata schemas (e.g. [Dublin Core](#), [DataCite](#), [Crossref](#), [JATS XML](#), ONIX, MARC (for books), etc.), via standard protocols for metadata exchange ([Open Access Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting – OAI-PMH](#), [REST API](#), HTTPS, etc.). It should also support massive metadata export (as CSV files, ONIX XML feeds or in any other established format) and provide metadata records to libraries (e.g. MARC).

An online publishing infrastructure should support the communication between the editorial team and authors, reviewers, copyeditors and the production team, as well as all publishing workflows:

Submission (e.g. via a submission dashboard)

- Manuscript submission by authors
- Notifications to editors that a submission has been made
- Rejecting a submission

Review

- Assigning submissions to reviewers
- The submission of peer review reports
- Responding to reviews
- Re-uploading the manuscript
- Additional rounds of review
- Making the decision
- Accepting a submission
- Moving to Copyediting

Copyediting

- Assigning a manuscript to a copyeditor
- Checking proofs by the authors
- Moving to production

The platform should support user management (registration, assigning roles, etc.).

The editorial team should also be able to maintain an archive of submissions, correspondence and decisions on the platform.

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2. How can I assign persistent identifiers to published content?

Assigning persistent identifiers (PIDs) to published content is crucial for ensuring the long-term accessibility and citation of scholarly works.

Although there are multiple PID systems (e.g. [Handle](#), [ARK](#)) for published outputs, Digital Object Identifiers ([DOIs](#)) seem to be the most widely used for scholarly articles and book chapters. It is also highly recommended to publishers to use PIDs for authors and contributors (e.g. [ORCID](#)), as well as PIDs for organisations (e.g. [ROR](#)).

In order to be able to assign DOIs, a publisher needs to register with a registration agency, e.g. [CrossRef](#) or [DataCite](#). This involves an annual membership fee. Each member is assigned a PID prefix that is unique. After that, the publisher needs to submit metadata for each publication to the registration agency to get a unique DOI. The metadata typically include

- Title
- Authors
- Abstract
- Publication date
- URL of the content
- PIDs for authors
- PIDs for authors' organisations.

A DOI is a combination of the prefix with a unique suffix for each publication (e.g. 10.1234/journalname.articleID). All PIDs should be embedded in the content, i.e. displayed as interactive links on the publication's landing page and in the full text. If there are changes to the publication details, the publisher should update metadata deposited with the registration agency.

3. What are the common metadata formats used for exporting publication metadata?

The most commonly used metadata format for exporting publication metadata include XML, JSON, HTML and CSV. It is highly recommendable to enable metadata export to several formats. The choice of supported formats will depend on the protocols used to expose metadata and the requirements of the target aggregating services and search engines.

4. What are the standard protocols for retrieving metadata from publishing infrastructures?

The most commonly used metadata exchange protocols include [Open Access Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting – OAI-PMH](#), [REST API](#) and HTTPS. It is highly recommendable to enable multiple protocols for metadata exchange.

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5. What are the main open source publishing infrastructures?

A number of free and open-source (FOSS) solutions are available, such as [Open Journal Systems](#), [Janeway](#), [Kotahi](#), [PubSweet](#) for journals, and [Open Monograph Press](#), [PubPub](#), [Manifold](#), [Fulcrum](#), [Scalar](#), etc. for books.

The mentioned solutions offer out-of-the-box functionalities that can fairly easily be enriched with free add-ons. They are designed and maintained by non-profit organisations and communities who seek to provide sufficient documentation and support knowledge exchange through forum discussions.

6. What are the best practices for documenting and preserving content and metadata over time?

There are several ways to ensure metadata and content preservation over time:

- Archiving digital copies in designated repositories, usually maintained by national libraries, as required by legal deposit legislation. Although usually available free of charge, this option may not enable seamless access to the content.
- Using digital preservation services, the so-called dark archives, i.e. decentralised backup databases hosted on multiple secured servers to preserve the authentic original version of the content. In case the content becomes unavailable on the publisher's platform, these preservation services can deliver it to users, ensuring seamless access (e.g. [LOCKSS](#), [CLOCKSS](#), [Portico](#)). These services usually come at a cost. Fortunately, there are a number of initiatives struggling to reduce costs for OA publishers (e.g. [PKP Preservation Network](#)).

7. What are the main services that support content preservation?

Notable examples of digital preservation services include:

- [LOCKSS \(Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe\)](#)
- [CLOCKSS \(Controlled LOCKSS\)](#)
- [Portico](#)

There are several initiatives that aim to support content preservation, especially for open access publishers:

- [PKP Preservation Network](#) (for publishers using the Open Journal Systems software).
- [JASPER \(JournAIS are Preserved forever\)](#): Focuses on Diamond Open Access journals indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals.
- [Thoth Archiving Network](#): A community effort aiding small and scholar-led book publishers.

Visibility, communication, marketing and impact

1. What can I do to increase the visibility of my publications?

Traditional marketing activities by the publisher, promotional activities in multiple languages, newsletters, blogs, direct emails, mailing lists, content alerts, notifications, and RSS/Atom feeds are all useful mechanisms for raising awareness of published content.

Visibility can also be maximised in search engines and aggregators by using search engine optimisation techniques, such as by providing structured metadata and XML sitemaps, by implementing metadata exchange protocols, or by enabling APIs.

Discovery services, aggregator databases, abstracting and indexing databases, and citation indexes can also help with content visibility, particularly when these are specific services relevant for the target audiences. It is also helpful to make the published content available in open repositories and sharing services in order to increase its visibility.

2. What can help published content have a greater impact?

Impact statements or simple (multi)language summaries can bring the content of scholarly publications closer to the general audience when added alongside published content, and it can be helpful to provide translations of publications that are potentially interesting for non-academic audiences. Active use and regular updates of social media or social networking can also help with outreach to academia and society to communicate with a much broader audience.

Post-publication reviews or online comments can further boost interest in content by a wider audience. Organising events like book promotions, journal promotions, the launching of a new journal issue, or working with the media (such as by issuing press releases) can help reach broader sectors of society.

3. What metrics should I be aware of?

A comprehensive array of indicators can be employed as article/chapter-level metrics, tracking events such as visits, views, downloads, citations usage across countries, or social media mentions. Measurements are made for a singular research output rather than across a whole journal, for example. Analytics software and methods can be used to generate and collect metrics.

Equity, diversity, inclusion, and belonging (EDIB), gender, and multilingualism

1. What do equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB) mean in scholarly publishing?

In the context of scholarly publishing, EDIB is about reducing different kinds of bias at various points in the publishing process and in various sectors of the publishing community. Creating equity means removing systemic barriers and biases to give equal opportunities to everyone. Ensuring diversity means making sure that people of different genders, abilities, ethnicities, linguistic and cultural backgrounds, geographic locations, institutions and career stages are represented in the various sectors of the scholarly community. Being inclusive means giving all individuals the chance to be seen, heard and considered. Finally, creating a sense of belonging means treating everyone as a full member of the community and helping them to thrive and contribute.

2. What types of bias can occur in scholarly publishing?

Various types of bias have the potential to emerge in the context of scholarly publishing. This means that some groups in the community may be underrepresented while others are overrepresented – a situation that may change from one discipline to the next (e.g. women may be underrepresented in engineering, whereas men may be underrepresented in nursing). For instance, bias could take forms such as:

- inadequate representation of some genders in a study sample
- underrepresentation of authors from certain cultural backgrounds
- fewer editorial board members from given geopolitical regions or institutions
- lower numbers of citations of works published in certain languages
- fewer leadership or executive roles held by people of a particular race
- lack of accessibility in electronic publishing platforms.

The situation may be further exacerbated because the effects of various types of disadvantage can be intersectional and cumulative. For example, an individual scholar who identifies as a woman, who has a visual impairment, who publishes in a language other than English, and who is affiliated with a less prestigious institution could potentially be marginalised in multiple ways.

3. What are some of the consequences of bias in scholarly publishing?

Bias in scholarly publishing can have negative impacts on individuals, on research, and on society. For example, at an individual level, a publisher's decision to publish in a single language means that scholars who speak other languages will need to invest more time and effort to engage with or contribute to the scholarly literature. Such scholars may end up publishing less, and may therefore not be cited as often and may not receive certain recognitions (e.g. appointments to editorial boards). Research as a whole may also suffer when there is a lack of diversity. For instance, if a certain geographic region or culture is over represented on the

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editorial board of an international journal, this group may influence the types of topics or methods that are considered worthy of publication, or they may engage in other types of gatekeeping in accordance with their particular set of values, which may not be globally representative. In turn, society broadly speaking may be negatively impacted if certain types of research are underrepresented (e.g. research on women's health issues, or research on biodiversity in certain regions).

4. Who is responsible for ensuring EDIB in scholarly publishing?

EDIB is a shared responsibility. A wide variety of actors in the scholarly publishing ecosystem must work together to improve and maintain EDIB, including authors, peer reviewers, editors, editorial board members, librarians, and publishers. Nevertheless, publishers are particularly well-placed to drive EDIB-related improvements since they are able to set goals and design policies that can bring about meaningful change.

5. What types of actions can be taken to improve EDIB in scholarly publishing?

Examples of actions that can be taken include raising awareness or offering training or guidance about unconscious bias; adopting inclusive language; publishing plain language summaries; developing and sharing diversity statements, action plans, and policies for EDIB (e.g. requesting citation diversity statements from authors or implementing a policy of double-anonymized peer review); setting goals for and assessing and monitoring progress in EDIB (e.g. diversity goals for authors, peer reviewers, editorial board members); implementing inclusive and accessible websites, content and metadata; and promoting multilingualism in scholarly publishing (e.g. by publishing abstracts or full-texts in more than one language).

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2.18 Glossary

Glossary of terms used in the Toolsuite and other DIAMAS resources.

While exact definitions for these terms may differ depending on viewpoints, the authors of this tool suite have agreed on the definitions based on their expertise and relevant available sources, which are included under each term where appropriate.

We welcome feedback and thoughts on the glossary which will be considered during the regular update cycles.

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Accessibility

The design of products, devices, services, vehicles, or environments so as to be usable by people with disabilities. The concept of accessible design and practice of accessible development ensures both “direct access” (i.e. unassisted) and “indirect access” meaning compatibility with a person’s assistive technology (for example, computer screen readers).

Reference/derivation: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Accessibility>

Accessibility policy

Formal rules your organisation puts in place to achieve its accessibility requirements: The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) are part of a series of web accessibility guidelines published by the Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI) of the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), the main international standards organisation for the Internet.

Reference/derivation: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Web_Content_Accessibility_Guidelines

Article level metrics

These are indicators that measure and monitor the reach and impact of published research outputs through online interactions, counting things such as downloads, shares, usage across countries, social media mentions etc. Measurements are made for a singular research output rather than across a whole journal, for example.

Authors’ rights or copyright

A rights regime that grants exclusive rights to creators of original works, including literary, artistic, musical, and other creative expressions, allowing them to control how their works are used and distributed.

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) or Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) is a conceptual framework that claims to promote the fair treatment and full participation of all people, especially in the workplace, including populations who have historically been under-represented or subject to discrimination because of their background, identity, disability, etc.

Reference/derivation: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Diversity,_equity,_and_inclusion

File format

A file format is a standard way of encoding information so that it can be stored in a computer file. It defines the structure and type of data that the file contains: how information is organised, encoded, and represented. Thanks to this, the data stored in files can be consistently interpreted, accessed, and processed by software applications.

File formats widely used in the context of scholarly publishing include:

- PDF (Portable Document Format)

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- EPUB (Electronic Publication)
- HTML (Hypertext Markup Language)
- XML JATS (Journal Article Tag Suite)
- DOCX (Microsoft Word Open XML Document)
- LaTeX (Document Preparation System)
- CSV (Comma-Separated Values)

Reference/derivation:: <https://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/appendices/file-formats/>

Free and open-source software

Free and open-source software (FOSS) is software available under a licence that grants the right to use, modify, and distribute the software, modified or not, to everyone free of charge, as opposed to proprietary software, where the restrictive copyright or licensing is used and the source code is not available to users.

Reference/derivation: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Free_and_open-source_software

Gender diversity

Equitable or fair representation of people of different genders. It most commonly refers to an equitable ratio of men and women, but also includes people of other genders (e.g. intersex, nonbinary, trans).

Reference/derivation: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gender_diversity

General Data Protection Regulation

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC is part of the data protection package adopted in May 2016 aiming at making Europe fit for the digital age. This Regulation lays down rules relating to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data.

Reference/derivation: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>

Indexing / indexation

Indexing is the process of listing scholarly titles by discipline, type of publication, region, etc. Sometimes referred to as bibliographic or citation indexes, journal indexing aims to make published information widely available and easy to access. Inclusion in an index usually involves an assessment process for relevance and quality.

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Interoperability

Interoperability is the ability of different systems, devices, or software to communicate, exchange data, interact and work together smoothly and efficiently. It involves the establishment of common standards, protocols, and interfaces to facilitate smooth communication among systems.

Metadata

Metadata provides information about data. Specifically, it is machine-readable data that describes content, context and structure of resources and their management over time. In the context of scholarly publishing, metadata are pieces of information that describe published outputs (articles, books, journals, etc.).

Metadata standard

Metadata standard is a set of rules and guidelines that define the structure and format of metadata. It ensures that resources are described consistently and that descriptions are understandable and usable across different platforms.

A specific implementation of a metadata standard tailored to a particular context or use case is called **metadata schema**. It details how the elements defined in a standard should be used and it often includes additional rules and guidelines.

Widely used metadata standards include:

- [Dublin Core](#)
- [MARC](#)(Machine-Readable Cataloguing)
- [MODS](#)(Metadata Object Description Schema)
- [TEI](#)(Text Encoding Initiative)
- [PREMIS](#)(Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies)

Reference/derivation: RDA Metadata Standards Catalogue: <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

Metadata exchange protocol

A metadata exchange protocol is a set of rules and standards that governs the transfer of metadata between systems, applications, or services. These protocols facilitate the sharing, discovery, and use of metadata and ensure interoperability, and consistent interpretation of metadata across various systems and platforms.

Commonly used metadata exchange protocols

1. [OAI-PMH](#) (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting)
2. [OAI-ORE](#) (Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange)
3. [RESTful APIs](#) (Representational State Transfer APIs)
4. [SWORD](#) (Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit)
5. [SOAP](#) (Simple Object Access Protocol)

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6. [SPARQL](#) (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language)
7. [Z39.50](#)

Multilingualism

In scholarly publishing, the presence and use of more than one language to disseminate research rather than relying on a single language for scholarly communication. This could include translating individual publications into more than one language, but it also entails a publishing ecosystem where publishing takes place in a variety of languages even when the works published are not translations of one another (e.g. one journal article may be published in Finnish, another in Polish, and another in French).

Reference/derivation: Inspired by the Helsinki Initiative (<https://www.helsinki-initiative.org/>)

Open licence

Legal text that can be used by copyright holders to grant rights to the public for using their works beyond what is allowed by the applicable copyright law by default.

Open Science

Open science (OS) is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.

Reference/derivation: [Unesco Recommendation on Open Science](#)

Persistent identifier

A persistent identifier (PID) is a long-lasting reference to a digital object, person, organisation, or other entity. It is unique to an entity and remains stable over time, i.e. it resolves even if the location of the entity changes.

PIDs widely used in scholarly publishing

- [DOI](#) (Digital Object Identifier)
- [Handle](#)
- [ARK](#) (Archival Resource Key)
- [URN](#) (Uniform Resource Name)
- [ISBN](#) (International Standard Book Number)
- [ISSN](#) (International Standard Serial Number)

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- [ORCID](#) (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)
- [ROR](#) (Research Organization Registry)
- [ISNI](#) (International Standard Name Identifier)

Reference/derivation: PID Services Registry: <https://pidservices.org/>

Preprints

Preprints are often defined as complete and public drafts of scientific documents, not yet certified by peer review. However, some authors of preprints do not intend to publish them in a peer-reviewed publication. Additionally, a preprint can be large datasets with descriptions, protocols, (parts of) a thesis, presentations, reports of negative results, commentaries, videos, and more, which do not pass a standard peer review process. A preprint can also be peer-reviewed by a community, by a combination of artificial intelligence with human expert peer review, or by reviewers exclusively. Ambiguities and disagreements around the definition of preprints need to be addressed to offer more precise and less anachronistic terms in such an innovative area. The main purpose of preprints is to disseminate research results to the scientific community, establish ownership of results, and receive feedback from the professional community before submission to a journal. Preprints, “not filtered by their perceived quality or pertinence”, can reduce the competitive pressure imposed on researchers and reduce the negative consequences of filtering scholarly information.

Reference/derivation: Stojanovski, J., Marušić, A. (2024). Preprints Are Here to Stay: Is That Good for Science?. In: Eaton, S.E. (eds) Second Handbook of Academic Integrity. Springer International Handbooks of Education. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54144-5_145

Research integrity

Research integrity (RI) encompasses a set of principles and practices that ensure researchers conduct their work ethically and with methodological rigour, fostering trust and confidence in the research process and its outcomes. Key elements include honesty, rigour, transparency, accountability, and respect for all participants. These principles should guide researchers at all stages of their work, from conceptualization to dissemination. Upholding research integrity is crucial for maintaining the credibility and reliability of scientific knowledge and fostering a relationship of trust between the research community and society. Various frameworks and guidelines, such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and institutional codes of conduct, provide guidance and standards for maintaining research integrity.

Reference/derivation: <https://ukrio.org/research-integrity/>

Research misconduct

Scientific misconduct refers to the violation of standard codes of scholarly conduct and ethical behaviour in the publication of professional scientific research. It constitutes a breach of

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scientific integrity, encompassing violations of the scientific method and research ethics across the design, conduct, and reporting of research. Examples of scientific misconduct include fabrication (making up results), falsification (manipulating research materials or data), plagiarism (appropriating another person's ideas or words without proper credit), misrepresentation of data, failing to declare or appropriately manage conflicts of interest, and breaching legal, ethical and professional requirements needed for research. Motivations for scientific misconduct may include career pressure, ease of fabrication, and monetary gain.

Reference/derivation: <https://ukrio.org/research-integrity/what-is-research-misconduct/>

Responsible research

Responsible Research (RR) is an approach aimed at anticipating and assessing the potential implications and societal expectations regarding research and innovation, with the goal of fostering the design of inclusive and sustainable practices. It involves engaging societal actors in collaborative processes throughout the entire research and innovation lifecycle, from agenda setting to implementation and evaluation, to align outcomes with societal values and needs. RRI encompasses various dimensions such as governance, ethics, gender equality, open access, citizen participation, and scientific education. The overarching aim of RRI is to ensure that research and innovation are conducted ethically, sustainably, and in a socially desirable manner, thereby promoting creativity and opportunities that benefit society as a whole.

Reference/derivation: <https://tetrris.eu/what-is-responsible-research-and-innovation-rri/#>

Search engine optimisation

Search engine optimization (SEO) is the practice of optimising (adjusting) the online content to adhere to the technical requirements of search engines with the aim of improving its visibility and ranking on search engine results pages and increasing web traffic.

Reference/derivation: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Search_engine_optimization

Annex 3: Keywords

Term	Guidelines	Toolsuite articles
Accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Choosing a platform • Metadata formats and export • Marketing, communication and visibility • Usage and metrics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software and interoperability • Preservation and content formats • Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) • Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata • Multilingualism
Copyright	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Copyright, authors' rights policy • Use of open licences in open access publishing • Metadata formats and export 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open science practices
Free and open-source software (FOSS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of research protocols, methods and software • Choosing a platform • Availability of research protocols, methods and software • Metadata formats and export 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open science practices • Software and interoperability
Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revenue Streams • Basic editorial information that should be displayed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding • Ownership and governance
GDPR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data sharing policy • GDPR and Personal data • Usage and metrics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Editorial management
Diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Gender diversity • Multilingualism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) • Gender diversity • Multilingualism
Equity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Gender diversity • Multilingualism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) • Gender diversity • Multilingualism

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Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Gender diversity • Multilingualism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) • Gender diversity • Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata • Multilingualism
Indexing / indexation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata formats and export • Marketing, communication and visibility • Usage and metrics • Use of open licences in open access publishing • Usage and metrics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software and interoperability • Metadata • Preservation and content formats • Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact • Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Choosing a platform • Metadata formats and export • Marketing, communication and visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software and interoperability • Metadata • Preservation and content formats • Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact
Licensing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Copyright, authors' rights policy • Use of open licences in open access publishing • Metadata formats and export • Research data sharing policy • Self-archiving policy • Basic editorial information that should be displayed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open science practices
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data sharing policy • Availability of research protocols, methods and software • GDPR and Personal data • Choosing a platform • Metadata formats and export • Marketing, communication and visibility • Usage and metrics • Multilingualism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software and interoperability • Metadata • Preservation and content formats • Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact • Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata • Multilingualism
Metadata and file formats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choosing a platform • Metadata formats and export • Multilingualism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata • Preservation and content formats

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Multilingualism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Multilingualism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open science practices • Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact • Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) • Multilingualism
Open Access (OA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Use of open licences in open access publishing • Preprints • Self-archiving policy • Marketing, communication and visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open science practices • Research integrity • Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)
Open Science (OS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Use of open licences in open access publishing • Preprints • Self-archiving policy • Availability of research protocols, methods and software • Multilingualism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) • Open science practices • Research integrity
Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing community-led governance • Basic editorial information that should be displayed • Marketing, communication and visibility • Gender diversity • Multilingualism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is Diamond open access? • Funding • Ownership and governance
Peer review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA policies • Preprints • Basic editorial information that should be displayed • Gender diversity • Multilingualism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open science practices • Editorial quality
Persistent identifiers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data sharing policy • Choosing a platform • Metadata formats and export • Marketing, communication and visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata

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Preservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research data sharing policy ● Self-archiving policy ● Basic editorial information that should be displayed ● Choosing a platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Editorial management ● Preservation and content formats
Research data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research data sharing policy ● Handling negative research results ● Availability of research protocols, methods and software ● GDPR and Personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open science practices ● Research integrity
Research integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research data sharing policy ● Preprints ● Handling negative research results ● Availability of research protocols, methods and software ● GDPR and Personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open science practices ● Research integrity
Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Revenue streams ● Choosing a platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Funding ● Ownership and governance
Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Revenue streams ● Diamond OA policies ● Implementing community-led governance ● Preprints ● Handling negative research results ● Availability of research protocols, methods and software ● Basic editorial information that should be displayed ● Marketing, communication and visibility ● Usage and metrics ● Gender diversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Funding ● Ownership and governance ● Open science practices ● Editorial quality ● Editorial management ● Research integrity

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Visibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Diamond OA policy• Preprints• Self-archiving policy• Choosing a platform• Metadata formats and export• Marketing, communication and visibility• Usage and metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact• Multilingualism
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